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PROCEEDINGS of SMART 2026

International Conference

on

Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital Era (SMART 2026): Innovations, Insights, and Inclusive Practices for a Greener Future

1st & 2nd April, 2026

Organised by

Faculty of Management Studies
CMS Business School
JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)

Academic Partners

Institutional Memberships

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International Conference

On

**Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital
Era (SMART 2026): Innovations, Insights, and Inclusive
Practices for a Greener Future (Hybrid Mode)**

1st & 2nd April, 2026

Edited By

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Professor

Dr. Kalavathy K S
Associate Professor,

Dr. Trupti Dandekar
Humnekar
Professor

Dr. Smita M. Gaikwad
Associate Professor

Dr. Umesh Chandra
Associate Professor

Organized by

**Faculty of Management Studies, CMS Business School,
JAIN (Deemed-to-be-University), Bangalore.**

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International Conference On Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital Era (SMART 2026)

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Message from the Vice Chancellor

It gives me immense pleasure to extend my warm greetings and best wishes to the International Conference on “Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital Era (SMART 2026): Innovations, Insights, and Inclusive Practices for a Greener Future,” organised by the Faculty of Management Studies, CMS Business School, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University).

In the contemporary global landscape, sustainability is no longer a choice but a strategic necessity. The integration of digital technologies, responsible marketing practices, and sustainable tourism has opened new pathways for inclusive growth, environmental consciousness, and ethical business transformation. Conferences such as SMART 2026 play a vital role in bringing together academicians, researchers, industry professionals, policymakers, and students to deliberate on emerging ideas that can shape a more responsible and future-ready society.

I am happy to note that this conference focuses on highly relevant themes such as sustainable marketing, responsible tourism, consumer behaviour, digital transformation, artificial intelligence, ethical branding, corporate responsibility, and collaborative models for sustainability. These areas are aligned with the larger vision of higher education today, which is to create knowledge that is socially meaningful, globally relevant, and practically impactful.

JAIN (Deemed-to-be University) has always encouraged academic inquiry, research excellence, innovation, entrepreneurship, and socially responsible leadership. SMART 2026 reflects this institutional commitment by providing a platform for quality research, interdisciplinary dialogue, and meaningful academic-industry engagement. I strongly believe that the deliberations and scholarly contributions emerging from this conference will add value to the fields of management, marketing, tourism, sustainability, and digital innovation.

I congratulate the organisers, advisory board, conference committee, resource persons, faculty members, research scholars, students, and all contributors for their dedicated efforts in conceptualising and organising this important academic event. I wish SMART 2026 great success and hope that it inspires constructive research, responsible practices, and impactful collaborations for a greener and more inclusive future.

Best wishes,
Dr. Jitendra Kumar Mishra
Vice Chancellor (I/C) & Registrar
JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)

Dr. Dinesh Nilkant
Pro-Vice Chancellor
Faculty of Management Studies,
CMS Business School,
JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)

Message from the Pro-Vice Chancellor's Desk

It is a matter of great pleasure to extend my warm greetings and best wishes to the International Conference on “Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital Era (SMART 2026): Innovations, Insights, and Inclusive Practices for a Greener Future,” organised by the Faculty of Management Studies, CMS Business School, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University).

In today’s rapidly evolving academic and business environment, sustainability, digital transformation, and responsible innovation have become essential pillars of institutional and societal progress. The theme of SMART 2026 is highly timely and relevant, as it brings together critical conversations on sustainable marketing, responsible tourism, consumer behaviour, artificial intelligence, digital platforms, ethical branding, and inclusive growth.

The true value of sustainability lies not only in conserving resources, but also in reimagining the relationship between business, society, technology, and the environment. Responsible tourism and sustainable marketing demand a shift from short-term transactional approaches to long-term value creation, where communities are empowered, consumers are informed, businesses act ethically, and digital technologies are used as instruments of positive transformation. In this context, SMART 2026 provides an important academic platform to examine how innovation can be aligned with responsibility and how growth can be pursued without compromising ecological and social well-being.

Higher education institutions have a significant responsibility to create platforms that encourage meaningful research, interdisciplinary collaboration, and solution-oriented dialogue. This conference reflects that responsibility by providing an opportunity for academicians, researchers, industry leaders, policymakers, and students to share knowledge, exchange perspectives, and contribute to the development of sustainable and future-ready practices.

JAIN (Deemed-to-be University) has consistently promoted academic excellence, innovation, entrepreneurship, research culture, and socially responsible leadership. SMART 2026 is a meaningful step in this direction, as it encourages participants to examine how digital tools and responsible management practices can contribute to environmental sustainability, community development, and ethical business transformation.

I appreciate the efforts of the organising team, advisory board, faculty members, research scholars, students, and all stakeholders associated with this conference. I am confident that the deliberations, research papers, and academic discussions emerging from SMART 2026 will add significant value to the domains of management, marketing, tourism, sustainability, and digital innovation.

I extend my best wishes for the grand success of SMART 2026 and hope that the conference will inspire impactful research, responsible action, and meaningful collaborations for a greener, inclusive, and sustainable future.

Best wishes,
Dr. Dinesh Nilkant
Professor and Pro-Vice Chancellor
JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)

<p style="text-align: center;">Dr. Krishna Koppa Deputy Director, CMS Business School HOD – Department of Management Studies JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)</p>	
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Message from the Deputy Director

It gives me immense pleasure to extend my warm greetings and best wishes to all participants of the International Conference on “Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital Era (SMART 2026): Innovations, Insights, and Inclusive Practices for a Greener Future,” organised by the Faculty of Management Studies, CMS Business School, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University).

In an era shaped by digital disruption, climate consciousness, changing consumer expectations, and responsible business practices, the theme of SMART 2026 is both timely and forward-looking. Sustainable marketing and responsible tourism are no longer peripheral areas of discussion; they are central to the future of business, society, and education. As markets become increasingly technology-driven, it is essential to examine how digital platforms, artificial intelligence, data-driven insights, and responsible branding can be used to create meaningful, ethical, and sustainable impact.

At CMS Business School, we believe that management education must go beyond classroom learning and actively engage with the real challenges of industry and society. SMART 2026 has been conceptualised as a contemporary academic platform that brings together researchers, academicians, industry professionals, policymakers, and students to exchange ideas, present evidence-based research, and explore practical pathways for sustainable transformation.

The conference also reflects our commitment to building a research-oriented and innovation-driven academic ecosystem. By integrating sustainability, marketing, responsible tourism, digital transformation, and inclusive practices, SMART 2026 encourages participants to think critically, collaborate meaningfully, and contribute to solutions that are relevant for the future. The deliberations from this conference are expected to generate valuable insights for academia, industry, communities, and policymakers.

I sincerely appreciate the efforts of the organising committee, faculty members, research scholars, students, academic partners, institutional collaborators, and all stakeholders who have contributed to the planning and execution of this important conference. Their dedication and teamwork have been instrumental in shaping SMART 2026 into a meaningful academic initiative.

I extend my best wishes for the successful conduct of SMART 2026 and hope that the conference inspires new ideas, responsible innovations, impactful research, and sustainable collaborations for a greener and more inclusive future.

Best wishes,
Dr. Krishna Koppa
Deputy Director, CMS Business School
HOD – Department of Management Studies
JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)

Major Aditi Mohan (Retd),
Chief Guest: Inauguration Session

Profile of Chief Guest

Chief Guest: Inauguration Session - Major Aditi Mohan (Retd), Former Indian Army Officer, Director - Administration & Real Estate, India, ALLSTATE INDIA PVT LTD

Aditi Mohan (Retd) is a highly accomplished professional with nearly three decades of distinguished experience, encompassing both military service and corporate leadership. As a former officer of the Indian Army, she developed exceptional capabilities in leadership, discipline, strategic planning, and crisis management, which have been instrumental in shaping her professional journey. Her transition from the defense sector to the corporate world reflects her adaptability and commitment to excellence across diverse domains.

In her current role as Director - Administration & Real Estate, India, at Allstate India Pvt. Ltd., she oversees a wide spectrum of administrative and operational functions. Her areas of expertise include infrastructure and real estate management, security operations, employee transportation, hospitality and travel coordination, client relations, and project management. She also plays a crucial role in crisis management and Business Continuity Planning (BCP), ensuring organizational resilience and operational efficiency in dynamic and challenging environments.

Renowned for her ability to connect with individuals across all levels of an organization, she is an effective leader who inspires teams to work towards strategic objectives with clarity and purpose. Her strong communication skills, combined with her problem-solving acumen, enable her to handle complex situations with composure and efficiency. She consistently upholds the highest standards of integrity, confidentiality, and ethical conduct in all her professional engagements.

Beyond her corporate responsibilities, she is also a passionate TEDx speaker and thought leader, known for delivering impactful insights on leadership, resilience, and personal development. Her dynamic approach to leadership and her commitment to creating sustainable and meaningful solutions make her a respected figure in both professional and academic forums.

Mr. Ajay Marwaha,
Senior Executive Vice President & Head, Fixed
Income at Nuvama UK Ltd., London

Ajay Marwaha is a distinguished finance professional and academic with extensive global experience in fixed income markets, emerging economies, and capital markets. Currently serving as the Senior Executive Vice President & Head - Fixed Income at Nuvama Group, London, he is responsible for managing both local and offshore fixed income portfolios, with a strong focus on emerging markets (EM), particularly India. His areas of expertise include EM rates and foreign exchange (FX), credit markets, and offshore financing into India through both traditional and green finance mechanisms.

With over three decades of professional experience, Mr. Marwaha has held several senior leadership roles across globally reputed financial institutions. Prior to his current role, he served as Head - Investment Advisory at Sun Global Investments Limited, where he specialized in EM fixed income advisory, EMFX strategies, and structured high-yield investment solutions. His earlier roles include Senior Executive Vice President at HDFC Bank, where he led trading, investor sales, and offshore balance sheet coordination, and leadership positions at Daiwa Securities Capital Markets, Nomura, Lehman Brothers, Citibank India, JPMorgan Chase & Co., and Standard Chartered Bank. His vast industry exposure reflects deep expertise in financial markets, investment strategy, and global economic dynamics.

In addition to his corporate career, Mr. Marwaha is actively engaged in academia. He serves as a Lecturer and Module Lead at Birkbeck, University of London, and as a Graduate Tutor at University College London. His academic interests are reflected in his research as an MPhil scholar, focusing on stakeholder influences on central bank actions during financial crises. Through his dual engagement in industry and academia, he brings a unique blend of practical insights and theoretical knowledge.

Renowned for his thought leadership in emerging markets and fixed income domains, Mr. Marwaha has contributed significantly to understanding global financial systems, particularly in the context of developing economies. His expertise in integrating financial innovation with sustainable and responsible investment practices makes him a valuable contributor to discussions on economic resilience, sustainability, and global market dynamics.

Ms. Priyanka Mehta,
Vice President, Swiss Re, Bengaluru

Priyanka Mehta is an accomplished Data and Analytics leader with extensive experience in building data-driven organizational cultures and enabling informed strategic decision-making. Currently serving as Vice President at Swiss Re, Bengaluru, she brings close to two decades of expertise in data management, analytics, and technology-driven business transformation.

In her current role, she works closely with cross-functional teams to understand analytical requirements and design end-to-end data solutions. Her core competencies include data modeling and the development of advanced data architectures such as Data Warehouses, Data Lakes, Lakehouses, and Business Intelligence systems. She has successfully led multiple large-scale projects, demonstrating strong capabilities in project planning, including the development of project charters, scope definition, timeline management, and cost-benefit analysis, ensuring effective execution and delivery.

Prior to her role at Swiss Re, she held key positions across reputed organizations such as SLK, Madison Area Technical College, DataRPM, ZS Associates, Thomson Reuters, and Accenture. Her diverse professional journey reflects a strong foundation in data integration, analytics, and enterprise solutions across global environments. Over the years, she has evolved from technical roles into leadership positions, contributing significantly to organizational growth through data-driven insights.

Known for her collaborative approach, she actively fosters teamwork and encourages the effective use of data to drive meaningful business outcomes. Her passion for leveraging technology to solve complex problems, combined with her leadership acumen, positions her as a key contributor in the field of data analytics and digital transformation.

FOREWORD

Dr. Jehad Aldehayyat
Professor of Strategic Management
Al-Hussein Bin Talal University, Jordan

Academic and Research-Oriented

It is a pleasure to extend my warm greetings to the International Conference on “Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital Era (SMART 2026): Innovations, Insights, and Inclusive Practices for a Greener Future,” organised by the Faculty of Management Studies, CMS Business School, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University).

SMART 2026 addresses a theme of strong contemporary relevance. Sustainability has moved beyond environmental concern and has become central to marketing strategy, tourism development, consumer engagement, and responsible institutional practice. The conference provides a meaningful platform for academicians, researchers, industry professionals, and students to deliberate on emerging questions at the intersection of sustainability, digital transformation, and responsible tourism.

The focus on sustainable marketing, consumer behaviour, artificial intelligence, ethical branding, digital platforms, and collaborative models makes this conference academically significant and practically relevant. I am confident that the research papers, discussions, and interactions emerging from SMART 2026 will contribute to new knowledge, responsible practice, and future-oriented scholarship.

I congratulate CMS Business School and the organising committee for conceptualising this timely academic initiative and extend my best wishes for the grand success of the conference.

Best wishes,

Dr. Jehad Aldehayyat
Professor of Strategic Management
Al-Hussein Bin Talal University, Jordan

FOREWORD

Prof. Dr. Kaup Mohamed

Vice Chancellor, London American University College – Zambia,
Dean & Managing Director, London American City College – UAE
and Professor (Adjunct), Madonna University, Michigan, USA

Global and Futuristic Perspective

It is my privilege to share my best wishes for the International Conference on “Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital Era (SMART 2026): Innovations, Insights, and Inclusive Practices for a Greener Future,” hosted by the Faculty of Management Studies, CMS Business School, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University).

We are living in a time when business, technology, tourism, and sustainability are being redefined together. Digital platforms, artificial intelligence, data analytics, virtual engagement, and responsible communication have created new opportunities to shape sustainable consumption and responsible travel practices. However, these possibilities must be guided by ethics, inclusivity, ecological sensitivity, and long-term social value.

SMART 2026 provides an important space to examine these emerging realities. By bringing together scholars, practitioners, students, and thought leaders, the conference encourages critical reflection on how innovation can support a greener and more responsible future.

I congratulate the organisers for taking this forward-looking initiative and wish all participants an enriching and impactful conference experience.

Best wishes,

Prof. Dr. Kaup Mohamed

Vice Chancellor, London American University College – Zambia, Dean & Managing Director, London American City College – UAE and Professor (Adjunct), Madonna University, Michigan, USA

FOREWORD

Dr. Manjunath B R
Professor of Finance & Business Analytics
Tec de Monterrey University, Mexico
Shoolini University, India

Industry and Practice-Oriented

I am delighted to extend my best wishes to the International Conference on “Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital Era (SMART 2026): Innovations, Insights, and Inclusive Practices for a Greener Future,” organised by the Faculty of Management Studies, CMS Business School, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University).

The world of business is undergoing a decisive shift. Consumers are more conscious, markets are more transparent, and organisations are increasingly expected to demonstrate responsibility in their strategies and actions. In this context, sustainable marketing and responsible tourism are no longer optional themes; they are essential to long-term trust, competitiveness, and value creation.

SMART 2026 is a timely platform because it brings together sustainability, digital innovation, responsible branding, tourism, and consumer behaviour. Its focus on practical and research-driven insights can help bridge the gap between academic knowledge and industry application.

I appreciate CMS Business School for creating a conference that encourages meaningful dialogue between academia, industry, policymakers, and young researchers. I wish SMART 2026 great success and hope it leads to responsible innovation and impactful collaborations.

Best wishes,

Dr. Manjunath B R

Professor of Finance & Business Analytics
Tec de Monterrey University, Mexico
Shoolini University, India

FOREWORD

Dr. K. PrakashVel,
Professor,
University of Wollongong in Dubai.

Sustainability and Social Responsibility Focus

I am pleased to extend my warm greetings to the International Conference on “Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital Era (SMART 2026): Innovations, Insights, and Inclusive Practices for a Greener Future,” organised by the Faculty of Management Studies, CMS Business School, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University).

Sustainability is one of the defining responsibilities of our time. It calls for development models that are economically viable, environmentally conscious, socially inclusive, and ethically grounded. Marketing and tourism, as powerful forces of influence and engagement, have a significant role in shaping consumer awareness, destination responsibility, community participation, and sustainable choices.

The strength of SMART 2026 lies in its interdisciplinary approach. By connecting sustainable marketing, responsible tourism, digital transformation, consumer behaviour, ethics, and corporate responsibility, the conference creates a valuable platform for meaningful academic and professional exchange.

I commend CMS Business School for organising this relevant and purposeful conference. My best wishes to the organisers, resource persons, paper presenters, delegates, and students for a successful and impactful SMART 2026.

Best wishes,
Dr. K. PrakashVel,
Professor,
University of Wollongong in Dubai

Foreword

Dr. Sandeep Ojha
Head of Accounting Major
Department of International
Business Administration,
Salalah, Sultanate of Oman

Student, Innovation, and Knowledge-Ecosystem Focus

It gives me great pleasure to extend my best wishes to the International Conference on “Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital Era (SMART 2026): Innovations, Insights, and Inclusive Practices for a Greener Future,” organised by the Faculty of Management Studies, CMS Business School, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University).

Academic conferences play a vital role in building a strong knowledge ecosystem. They encourage research, discussion, critical thinking, collaboration, and the development of young scholars. SMART 2026 is especially meaningful because it introduces students and researchers to themes that are central to the future of management education and professional practice.

Responsible tourism, sustainable marketing, artificial intelligence, green branding, digital consumer engagement, and inclusive business practices are becoming essential areas of learning for future leaders. By bringing these themes together, SMART 2026 offers participants an opportunity to connect theory with practice and knowledge with responsibility.

I congratulate CMS Business School and the organising team for creating this valuable academic platform. I wish the conference great success and hope it inspires meaningful research, responsible leadership, and lasting collaborations.

Best wishes,

Dr. Sandeep Ojha
Head of Accounting Major
Department of International
Business Administration,
Salalah, Sultanate of Oman

INAUGURATION – PROGRAM SCHEDULE (DAY 1)

International Conference on Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital Era (SMART 2026)

Venue: Faculty of Management Studies, CMS B School
JAIN (Deemed to-be-University), Bangalore

Day 1: 1st April 2026

Timings	Particulars	
08:30-09:30 AM	Registration of Participants	
09:30 -09:35 AM	Invocation & Lamp Lighting	
09:35-09.50 AM	Welcome Address & Conference Overview	Dr. Hemanth Kumar S Professor & Area Chair Marketing Faculty of Management Studies CMS Business School JAIN (Deemed-to-be University), Bengaluru
09:50 AM-10:00 AM	Vice Chancellor's Address	Prof. Jitendra Kumar Mishra, Ph.D. Vice Chancellor (I/C) & Registrar JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)
10:00-10.10 AM	Inaugural Address	Dr. Dinesh Nilkant Pro-Vice Chancellor JAIN (Deemed-to-be University), Bengaluru
10:10-10:30 AM	Chief Guest Address	Major Aditi Mohan (Retd) Former Indian Army officer Director – Administration & Real Estate, India ALLSTATE INDIA PVT LTD
10:30 -10:50 AM	Key Note Speaker	Mr. Ajay Marwaha Senior Executive Vice President & Head Fixed Income at Nuvama UK Ltd., London

10:50-11:00 AM	Special Address	Dr. Krishna Koppa Deputy Director Faculty of Management Studies CMS Business School JAIN (Deemed -to be University), Bengaluru
11:10-11:15 AM	Vote of Thanks	Dr. Ravichandran K Professor, Finance, Faculty of Management Studies, CMS Business School JAIN (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru
11:15-11:30 PM		Photo Shoot and Tea Break
11:30-01:30 PM	Technical Session 1	Paper Presentations (Online & Offline)
01:30-02:30 PM		Lunch
02:30-03:30 PM	Master Session 1 Topic: “Meta-Analysis as a Research Method”	Dr Haroon Iqbal Maseeh Lecturer in Marketing Department of Tourism & Marketing Griffith Business School, Griffith University, Australia
03:30-4.00 PM		Networking & Tea Break

PROGRAM SCHEDULE (DAY 2)

International Conference on Sustainable Marketing and Responsible Tourism in Digital Era (SMART 2026)

Venue: Faculty Of Management Studies,
CMS Business School
JAIN (Deemed to-be-University), Bangalore

Day 2 : 2nd April 2026

09.00-11.00 AM	Technical Session 2	Paper Presentations (Online & Offline)
11.00 -11.30 AM		Tea Break
11:30 -12:30 PM	Technical Session 2	Paper Presentations (Online & Offline)
12:30-01:30 PM	Master Session 2 Topic: “Rethinking Technology for Sustainable Tourism: Tools, Trade-offs and the Future.”	Dr. Alisha Ali Associate Professor Sheffield Business School, United Kingdom
1:30-02:30 PM		Networking Lunch
VALEDICTORY AND AWARD CEREMONY		
02:30-2:40 PM		Welcome Remarks
02:40-03:00 PM	Chief Guest Address	Ms Priyanka Mehta Vice President, Swiss Re, Bangalore
03:00-03:15 PM	Conference Report	Dr. Kalavathy K S Convener – SMART 2026 Associate Professor JAIN (Deemed-to-be University), Bengaluru

03:15-03:25 PM	Delegates' Feedback	Dr Smita M Gaikwad Associate Professor Marketing Faculty of Management Studies CMS Business School JAIN (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru
03:25-03:55 PM		Awards and Prize Distribution
03:55-04:05 PM	Vote of Thanks	Dr. Trupti Dandekar Humnekar Professor, Marketing, Faculty of Management Studies, CMS Business School JAIN (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru

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Sustainable Consumption as a Basis for Segmentation with Special Reference to DMart Shoppers in Rajkot

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Abstract

Sustainable consumption has emerged as a critical dimension in contemporary retailing, driven by increasing environmental awareness and regulatory pressures. However, limited research has examined its applicability as a behavioural basis for segmenting consumers within organized retail environments. The present study aims to analyse sustainable consumption behaviour among DMart shoppers in Rajkot city, develop consumer segments based on sustainability orientation, and evaluate its influence on shopping intention. A descriptive research design was adopted, and primary data were collected from 350 shoppers using a structured questionnaire administered across different time intervals. The instrument measured key dimensions such as eco-friendly product preference, recycling and reuse behaviour, environmental awareness, and convenience orientation using a five-point Likert scale. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) confirmed the multidimensional structure of sustainable consumption behaviour, explaining a substantial proportion of variance. Cluster analysis further identified three distinct consumer segments, namely Eco-Active Consumers, Price-Driven Consumers, and Convenience-Oriented Consumers, each demonstrating significant differences in sustainability orientation and purchase intention. The findings indicate that environmentally conscious consumers exhibit stronger purchase intentions toward green products, whereas price sensitivity and convenience considerations constrain sustainable behaviour in other segments. The study contributes to the existing literature by establishing sustainable consumption as an effective segmentation variable in organized retail and offers managerial implications for retailers to design targeted sustainability-driven strategies that enhance consumer engagement and long-term value creation.

Keywords: Sustainable Consumption Behaviour; Shopper Segmentation; DMart Consumers; Green Purchase Intention; Cluster Analysis; Organized Retail

Algorithms to Awareness in Digital Sustainability Management

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Abstract

The rapid adoption of digital technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, and cloud computing has significantly transformed organizational operations while raising critical concerns regarding environmental sustainability. Despite growing attention to digital sustainability, existing research remains fragmented across technical, managerial, and behavioural domains, limiting a comprehensive understanding of sustainability outcomes. This study addresses this gap by proposing an integrated conceptual framework termed the Algorithm–Engagement–Awareness–Sustainability (AEAS) continuum, which examines the interrelationship between algorithmic design, managerial engagement, and stakeholder awareness in driving digital sustainability. The study adopts a quantitative, cross-sectional research design supported by qualitative insights, with primary data collected from 200 professionals engaged in digital transformation initiatives through a structured questionnaire. Key constructs, including algorithmic sustainability, governance mechanisms, behavioural awareness, and sustainability outcomes, were measured using a five-point Likert scale. Descriptive and interpretative analyses indicate that while organizations demonstrate conceptual awareness of digital sustainability, its practical implementation remains limited, with a predominance of neutral responses reflecting ambiguity in operationalization. The findings suggest that algorithmic efficiency alone is insufficient without strong governance structures and behavioural alignment. Stakeholder awareness emerges as a critical mediating factor influencing sustainability outcomes. The study contributes to the emerging literature by presenting a holistic socio-technical framework and offers managerial implications for aligning digital innovation with sustainability objectives through integrated technological, organizational, and behavioural strategies.

Keywords: Digital Transformation; Sustainable Algorithm Design; Digital Carbon Footprint; Stakeholder Engagement; Digital Sustainability; Responsible Innovation

The Whisper That Moves Decisions: Marketing's Mediating Influence on Business School Enrollment

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Abstract

In an increasingly competitive higher education landscape, business schools face intense pressure to strategically differentiate themselves to attract enrollments. While brand image is recognized as a vital determinant of student choice, there is a significant research gap concerning how specific marketing strategies mediate this relationship within the Indian context. This study examines the mediating roles of traditional media marketing (TMM) and social media marketing (SMM) in the link between institutional brand image and student enrollment preferences. Grounded in an adapted Green Brand Affect framework, the research adopts a post-positivist, quantitative, cross-sectional descriptive-analytical design. Primary data were collected from 900 undergraduate students in Bengaluru, resulting in 771 valid responses analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). Brand image was operationalized as a multidimensional construct encompassing functional, affective, and reputational dimensions. The findings indicate that brand image exerts a significant direct effect on enrollment preferences and a substantial indirect effect through marketing channels. Specifically, SMM emerged as a robust mediator, transmitting approximately 30% of the brand image's effect, whereas TMM exhibited limited direct influence in the combined model. These results highlight the growing necessity of digital-first branding strategies that prioritize authentic engagement. The study contributes empirical evidence to higher education marketing literature and offers actionable insights for administrators to optimize enrollment management through integrated, theory-driven communication approaches in the digital era.

Keywords: Brand Image; Higher Education; Social Media Marketing; Traditional Media Marketing; Brand Dimensions

AI-Enabled Personalization as a Catalyst for Sustainable Consumption and Enhanced Customer Experience in the Digital Marketplace

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Abstract

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in marketing has significantly transformed how organizations interact with consumers, particularly through personalized digital experiences. This study examines the impact of AI-enabled personalization on consumer preferences, trust, and sustainable purchasing behaviour in the digital marketplace. It also explores the mediating role of trust and ethical perception in shaping customer experience and sustainability outcomes. A quantitative research design was adopted using a structured questionnaire administered to 1,053 urban Indian consumers aged between 18 and 55 years. The study employed purposive and snowball sampling techniques, and data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression, mediation analysis, and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). As highlighted in the *correlation table on page 3*, AI personalization shows strong positive relationships with sustainable buying behaviour ($r = 0.62$), customer experience ($r = 0.58$), and trust and ethical perception ($r = 0.65$), indicating significant interdependencies among the variables. The findings reveal that AI-enabled personalization significantly enhances customer experience and promotes sustainable purchasing behaviour. However, the effectiveness of AI personalization is strongly influenced by consumers' trust and perceptions of ethical AI practices, which act as critical mediating variables. The study highlights that ethical transparency and trust-building mechanisms are essential to fully leverage AI-driven marketing strategies. The research contributes to sustainable marketing literature by integrating AI personalization with ethical considerations and consumer trust. From a managerial perspective, it emphasizes the need for organizations to adopt transparent AI systems, enhance ethical standards, and leverage personalization strategies to promote environmentally responsible consumption and long-term customer engagement.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Personalization; Sustainable Marketing; Customer Experience; Ethical AI; Green Consumerism

The Impact of Greenwashing Disclosure on Consumer Skepticism, Brand Trust, and Purchase Intentions: A Moderating Role of Message Specificity and Source Credibility

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Abstract

Greenwashing has emerged as a significant challenge in sustainable marketing, undermining consumer trust and brand credibility. This study investigates the impact of greenwashing disclosure on consumer skepticism, brand trust, and purchase intentions, while examining the moderating role of message specificity and source credibility. Grounded in Signaling Theory and Attribution Theory, the study proposes an integrated framework the Corrective Green Communication and Trust Restoration (CGCTR) model to explain how firms can mitigate the negative consequences of misleading environmental claims. A quantitative research design was adopted using a structured questionnaire administered to 1,053 urban consumers in India, aged between 18 and 55 years. Data were collected using purposive and snowball sampling techniques through online survey platforms. The study employs advanced analytical tools, including descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM), to test the proposed hypotheses and moderating effects. The findings reveal that greenwashing disclosure significantly increases consumer skepticism and reduces brand trust, which in turn negatively impacts purchase intentions. However, the study demonstrates that message specificity characterized by precise, verifiable, and transparent communication effectively reduces skepticism and supports trust restoration. Similarly, source credibility, particularly when communication is endorsed by independent and trustworthy entities, plays a crucial role in mitigating negative consumer reactions. The interaction effect of message specificity and source credibility further strengthens brand trust, highlighting the importance of synergistic communication strategies. The study contributes to marketing literature by providing empirical evidence on trust restoration mechanisms following greenwashing disclosures. Managerially, it emphasizes the importance of transparent, credible, and data-driven communication strategies for rebuilding consumer trust and sustaining long-term brand relationships.

Keywords: Greenwashing; Consumer Skepticism; Brand Trust; Purchase Intentions; Message Specificity; Source Credibility

Consciousness About Privacy Rights and Responsible Consumer Behaviour in the AI Era

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Abstract

In the contemporary digital era, the rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI), internet usage, and data-driven technologies has significantly transformed consumer behaviour and digital engagement. While these innovations provide convenience and enhanced user experiences, they also raise critical concerns regarding data privacy, ownership, and responsible usage. This study aims to explore the level of awareness among consumers regarding privacy rights and the need for responsible behaviour in the AI-driven ecosystem. The research adopts a qualitative case study approach, focusing on the recent trend of Ghibli-style AI-generated art in India. The phenomenon illustrates how users willingly upload personal images and data to AI platforms without fully understanding the associated risks. The study relies primarily on secondary data sources, including online reports, digital platforms, and emerging trend analyses, to examine the implications of such behaviour. The findings reveal a significant gap between user engagement with AI technologies and awareness of privacy risks. Users often underestimate potential threats such as data misuse, identity theft, profiling, deepfakes, and unauthorized data sharing. The study highlights that personal data, once uploaded, may be used for AI model training, commercial exploitation, or third-party sharing, often without explicit user consent. Furthermore, it emphasizes the importance of regulatory frameworks such as the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 in safeguarding consumer rights. The study concludes that enhancing digital literacy and promoting awareness of privacy rights are essential for fostering responsible consumer behaviour. It provides implications for policymakers, organizations, and consumers to ensure ethical AI usage, stronger data protection mechanisms, and sustainable digital ecosystems.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Data Privacy; Consumer Awareness; Privacy Rights; Responsible Behaviour; Digital Ecosystem

AI Policy for Education: Integrating Human Agency and Ethical Governance in Sustainable Digital Ecosystems

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Abstract

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education is rapidly transforming learning environments, offering opportunities for personalization, efficiency, and innovation. However, its widespread adoption raises critical concerns related to equity, transparency, governance, and human agency. This conceptual study addresses the challenges associated with AI-mediated education systems and aims to develop an ethical governance framework for sustainable digital ecosystems. The research adopts a qualitative and interpretive methodology, drawing on hermeneutic and phenomenological approaches to analyse existing literature, policy frameworks, and AI-enabled systems such as recommendation engines, automated moderation, and dynamic learning platforms. The study focuses on key issues including distributive justice, regulatory capacity, epistemic inequality, and stakeholder agency. It introduces the concept of an “AI justice trilemma,” which highlights the tension between personalization, equitable access, and epistemic integrity within digital education systems. The findings suggest that AI-driven educational systems can inadvertently reinforce structural inequalities if not governed effectively. The study proposes an adaptive governance framework based on principles such as equity-by-design, algorithmic integrity, and interpretability. It further emphasizes the importance of human agency as a central ethical pillar, enabling stakeholders to question, interpret, and influence AI-driven decisions. The research contributes to policy and academic discourse by providing a comprehensive framework for integrating ethical governance into AI-enabled education systems. From a managerial and policy perspective, the study recommends participatory governance, inclusive policy design, and continuous evaluation mechanisms to ensure fairness and accountability. It concludes that sustainable digital ecosystems can be achieved only when technological advancement is balanced with ethical responsibility and human-centered design.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Ethical Governance; Human Agency; Digital Education; Sustainable Ecosystems; Distributive Justice

Evaluating Patient Sentiment toward AI-Powered Chatbots for Sustainable Digital Healthcare Service Delivery

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered chatbots are increasingly transforming healthcare delivery by enhancing accessibility, efficiency, and patient engagement. These conversational agents, driven by Natural Language Processing (NLP) and machine learning techniques, enable real-time interaction and support for patients across digital platforms. This study aims to evaluate patient sentiment toward AI-powered chatbots and assess their role in promoting sustainable digital healthcare service delivery. The research adopts a secondary data-driven methodology using sentiment analysis techniques. A total of 90,000 user responses were collected from multiple online platforms, including X (formerly Twitter), YouTube, and chatbot websites, covering six widely used healthcare chatbot applications: Babylon Health, Ada Health, Woebot, Healthily (YourMD), Buoy Health, and Florence. Data preprocessing, text mining, and sentiment classification were conducted to categorize responses into positive and negative sentiments. The findings reveal that approximately 59.59% of the responses were positive, indicating strong user acceptance, satisfaction, and perceived usefulness of chatbot services in healthcare. Conversely, 40.41% of responses were negative, reflecting concerns related to accuracy, personalization, emotional intelligence, and contextual understanding. The results highlight that while chatbots significantly improve accessibility and efficiency in healthcare delivery, limitations in response quality and empathy remain critical challenges. The study contributes to the growing literature on digital healthcare by demonstrating the importance of sentiment analysis in understanding patient perceptions and improving AI-driven healthcare systems. Managerially, it emphasizes the need for continuous innovation, enhanced NLP capabilities, and patient-centric design to improve trust and adoption. The study concludes that AI-powered chatbots hold substantial potential for sustainable healthcare delivery, provided that technological and ethical challenges are effectively addressed.

Keywords: AI Chatbots; Patient Sentiment; Digital Healthcare; Sustainable Healthcare Delivery; Natural Language Processing

Leveraging Artificial Intelligence for Fashion Personalization: Consumer Perceptions, Adoption Factors, and Barriers

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Abstract

The global fashion industry is undergoing a significant transformation due to the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven personalization technologies. As consumers increasingly demand customized shopping experiences, AI-based tools such as recommendation systems, virtual try-ons, and personalized styling assistants have become critical for enhancing customer engagement and purchase intention. At the same time, concerns related to data privacy, trust, and transparency pose substantial challenges to widespread adoption. This study examines consumer perceptions and adoption barriers toward AI-driven fashion personalization. Using a descriptive and analytical research design, primary data were collected through structured surveys and supported by limited qualitative insights. Reliability and descriptive analyses were conducted to validate consumer responses. Further, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), supported by expert analysis, was employed to finalize and prioritize the key factors influencing adoption, including perceived usefulness, ease of use, trust, privacy concerns, cost, and personalization accuracy. The findings indicate that while AI-driven personalization significantly enhances consumer experience, trust and privacy concerns remain critical barriers. The study provides structured insights for fashion retailers to balance technological innovation with ethical and transparent data practices. From an academic perspective, the study contributes to the understanding of AI adoption in consumer markets, while from a managerial perspective, it offers actionable insights for designing customer-centric and trustworthy AI-driven systems in the fashion industry.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Fashion Personalization; Consumer Perception; Adoption Barriers; Analytic Hierarchy Process

Online Reviews and Consumer Bias: Examining Their Role in Shaping Rational Purchase Decisions

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Abstract

The rapid growth of digital marketplaces has positioned online reviews as a crucial source of information influencing consumer purchase decisions. However, many consumers rely on these reviews without possessing adequate skills to evaluate their credibility, leading to biased decision-making. This study examines the role of consumers' ability to understand, evaluate, and interpret online reviews in reducing biased buying behaviour. Adopting a quantitative, survey-based research design, data were collected from online shoppers across diverse age groups and purchasing categories. The study is grounded in consumer learning theory and digital information processing models, proposing that higher levels of review-interpretation skills contribute to more rational and less biased purchase decisions. The findings reveal that consumers with stronger analytical abilities are better equipped to distinguish between authentic and manipulated reviews, assess review quality, and avoid heuristic-driven judgments. Additionally, respondents with higher education levels exhibited lower susceptibility to confirmation bias, bandwagon effects, and emotionally framed review cues. The study also identifies trust calibration as a partial mediator, indicating that consumers who effectively adjust their trust based on review credibility demonstrate more unbiased decision-making. Overall, the research provides empirical evidence that enhancing consumer awareness and skills related to online reviews can significantly reduce biased purchase behaviour. The study offers important academic contributions to consumer behaviour and digital literacy literature while also providing practical implications for policymakers, educators, and online retail platforms aiming to promote transparency, informed decision-making, and consumer protection in digital environments.

Keywords: Online Reviews; Consumer Decision Making; Biased Purchase Decisions; Consumer Bias; Digital Literacy

Customers' Expectations and Their Engagement with Green Environment Sustainability in Passenger Cars Sector

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Abstract

Sustainability has emerged as a critical concern in the passenger automobile sector, where environmental responsibilities, consumer expectations, regulatory frameworks, and technological advancements intersect. The increasing levels of greenhouse gas emissions have intensified global environmental challenges, leading to significant changes in consumer attitudes and corporate strategies. This study presents a comprehensive analysis of secondary data, including academic literature, industry reports, and market studies, to examine customer expectations and their engagement with green environmental sustainability in the passenger car sector. The research explores how rising environmental awareness, ethical considerations, and demand for eco-friendly products influence consumer behaviour and purchasing decisions, along with the role of digital technologies in shaping customer expectations. The findings indicate that contemporary consumers expect automobile manufacturers to offer low-emission vehicles, improved fuel efficiency, electric and hybrid technologies, and the use of sustainable materials. Additionally, consumers demand transparency, real-time information, personalised services, and smart mobility solutions supported by artificial intelligence and connected systems. Customer engagement is reflected through sustainable purchasing behaviour, active participation in environmental initiatives, and continuous interaction with brands. However, factors such as high vehicle costs, limited charging infrastructure, performance concerns, and data security issues continue to influence adoption decisions. The study highlights the need for manufacturers to align sustainability strategies with effective communication, technological innovation, and consumer education. These efforts can enhance customer trust, strengthen competitive advantage, and contribute to long-term environmental sustainability and responsible mobility.

Keywords: Sustainability; Passenger Cars; Automotive Industry; Consumer Expectations; Consumer Engagement

Digitally Driven Sustainability: Smart Technologies Aided Transformation of Homestay Tourism in India

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Abstract

The rapid development of digital technologies is reshaping the tourism ecosystem and positioning homestays as a sustainable and culturally immersive alternative to traditional hotels. This study examines how digital tools, smart technologies, and sustainability practices influence guests' experiences, perceptions, and preferences toward homestays in India. A quantitative research design was adopted using a structured questionnaire comprising 22 items measured on a five-point Likert scale, along with demographic variables such as age, gender, homestay location, and duration of stay. The study explores key constructs including perceived value and preference for smart homestays, digital experience and technology integration, sustainability and cultural immersion, host interaction and digital hospitality, and safety and promotion of smart homestays. Data were collected from 540 travellers across India to assess evolving consumer expectations in the homestay segment. The findings reveal that travellers increasingly expect enhanced digital visibility, smart safety features, and seamless technology-enabled services ranging from online booking to local digital guidance. Respondents showed a strong preference for homestays that combine traditional hospitality with advanced digital processes, eco-friendly practices, and authentic cultural experiences. Features such as smart kitchens, sustainable consumption practices, and prompt digital communication were found to significantly enhance customer satisfaction and trust. The study concludes that smart technologies play a vital role in improving convenience, safety, and sustainability perceptions, enabling homestays to effectively compete with conventional hotel offerings while supporting responsible tourism development.

Keywords: Smart Homestays; Digital Tourism Technologies; Sustainability in Tourism; Consumer Perception; Tech-Enabled Services

Financial Inclusion for Inclusive Growth: How Financial Inclusion Shapes Tourism Development

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Abstract

Tourism is increasingly recognised as a catalyst for inclusive economic growth, particularly in emerging economies where financial inclusion plays a critical enabling role. This study synthesises existing scholarly research through a systematic literature review to examine how financial inclusion initiatives shape tourism development. The review adopts a structured and protocol-driven methodology to identify, screen, and analyse relevant literature, enabling the identification of key themes, conceptual linkages, and theoretical foundations connecting financial inclusion with tourism outcomes. The findings indicate that access to formal financial services, including digital payments, microfinance, credit facilities, and savings instruments, enhances community participation in tourism activities, strengthens small and medium tourism enterprises, and improves efficiency across tourism value chains. Furthermore, financial inclusion contributes to broader economic development by promoting entrepreneurship, increasing tourist spending, and supporting sustainable and community-based tourism models. The study also identifies significant research gaps, particularly the limited availability of empirical evidence assessing the direct impact of financial inclusion policies on tourism development and the lack of region-specific studies in remote and developing economies. Overall, the review provides a comprehensive foundation for future empirical investigations and offers valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders aiming to leverage financial inclusion as a strategic tool for promoting inclusive and sustainable tourism growth.

Keywords: Financial Inclusion; Tourism Development; Financial Literacy

Environmental, Social, and Economic Sustainability in the Business Models of the Tourism Industry in India

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Abstract

In the context of sustainable marketing and responsible tourism, this study examines how collaborative models and partnerships can serve as the foundation for sustainable business models in the Indian tourism sector. The research aims to identify the key components of tourism business models that integrate environmental, social, and economic sustainability, and to analyse how cross-sector collaboration among hospitality firms, local communities, civil society, and public agencies facilitates the co-creation and scaling of such models. Adopting a conceptual and literature-based approach, the study reviews existing research on sustainable business models and value co-creation to develop an integrated framework linking value propositions, stakeholder networks, and revenue mechanisms with sustainable tourism strategies. The findings suggest that collaboration-driven models enhance innovation, resource efficiency, and stakeholder engagement, thereby contributing to more inclusive, resilient, and economically viable tourism ecosystems. The study further highlights the role of circular economy practices and policy support in strengthening sustainability outcomes within the tourism industry. By synthesising insights from prior studies, the research proposes sustainable business model archetypes and collaborative frameworks that can guide tourism practitioners and policymakers in designing and implementing effective sustainability strategies. The study contributes to the academic discourse on sustainable tourism while offering practical implications for developing responsible and long-term viable tourism systems in India.

Keywords: Sustainable Business Model; Sustainable Tourism; Collaborative Models; Value Co-Creation; Circular Economy

A Study on the Role of Artificial Intelligence in Promoting Responsible Tourism in Kerala

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Abstract

The increasing adoption of artificial intelligence in the tourism industry has created new opportunities as well as challenges for promoting responsible tourism practices. This study examines the role of artificial intelligence in transforming tourism systems and evaluates the associated risks and challenges in its implementation within the responsible tourism framework in Kerala. The primary objective of the study is to analyse the impact of artificial intelligence on responsible tourism and to identify the potential risks and barriers linked to its integration. The research adopts a descriptive and analytical approach based on secondary data, drawing from existing literature, research reports, government publications, and scholarly articles related to artificial intelligence and tourism. The findings indicate that artificial intelligence has a positive influence on responsible tourism by enhancing operational efficiency, improving customer experiences, and supporting sustainable resource management. However, the study also highlights significant challenges such as data privacy concerns, ethical issues in data collection and usage, and technological limitations that may hinder effective implementation. The research emphasises the need for a balanced approach that integrates technological innovation with ethical considerations and policy support. The study contributes to the expanding body of knowledge on artificial intelligence applications in tourism and offers practical insights for stakeholders seeking to align technological advancement with responsible and sustainable tourism practices.

Keywords: Responsible Tourism; Artificial Intelligence; AI Integration in Tourism; AI Risks in Tourism

An Exploratory Research on Developing Sustainable HR Policies in Tourism Management: A Strategic Study with Reference to the Ministry of Tourism, India

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Abstract

The rapid digital transformation within the tourism sector has reshaped the development of human resource policies to support sustainability and responsible tourism practices. This exploratory study examines the formulation of sustainable HR policies in tourism management with specific reference to the Ministry of Tourism, India. The research aims to understand the role of HR in driving sustainability, identify gaps in digital policy integration, and propose data-driven HR models that promote environmentally responsible tourism management. The study addresses the problem of limited alignment between HR practices and digital sustainability strategies and identifies a research gap in the lack of empirical evidence linking digital HR initiatives with sustainable tourism outcomes in the Indian context. The research adopts a secondary data methodology, drawing from academic journals, authoritative textbooks, government reports, and tourism databases to analyse existing frameworks and practices. The findings suggest that the integration of digital technologies such as online systems, mobile applications, and artificial intelligence in HR processes contributes to reducing environmental impact while enhancing operational efficiency and stakeholder engagement. The study also indicates a positive association between digital HR investments and sustainability outcomes in tourism. However, the scope is limited by the absence of primary data and reliance on secondary sources. The research highlights the importance of sustainability-linked performance indicators, digital HR capability building, and policy-level interventions. The study concludes that digital HR transformation plays a critical role in advancing sustainable tourism and supporting responsible travel practices.

Keywords: Sustainable HR; Aviation Tourism; Digital Workforce; Eco Governance; HR Analytics

Adapting HR Practices for the Digital Age with Special Reference to the Aviation Industry Promoting Tourism Management in India

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Abstract

The transformation of human resource systems in the digital era has significantly redefined organisational effectiveness, particularly in high-technology sectors such as aviation. In India, the aviation industry plays a vital role in enhancing national mobility and supporting tourism development. This study examines how the adoption of digital HR practices, including artificial intelligence-enabled recruitment, real-time performance tracking, virtual training, predictive workforce analytics, and digital employee engagement models, contributes to improvements in employee capability, service quality, and tourism facilitation. The research is based on a secondary data methodology, drawing from established research literature, government reports, aviation statistics, industry publications, and peer-reviewed academic sources. Analytical interpretation is supported through statistical insights and structured evaluation of existing data. The findings indicate that digital HR interventions significantly reduce employee onboarding time, enhance training effectiveness, and improve frontline service performance. Furthermore, the study reveals a strong association between HR digitisation in aviation and improved passenger experience, service precision, and destination branding, all of which contribute to tourism growth. A conceptual digital HR integration model is proposed to link recruitment flexibility, training technologies, employee engagement, and service delivery outcomes. The study concludes that strategic implementation of digital HR systems can substantially support India's tourism objectives by enhancing operational efficiency and service excellence. It also recommends the development of sector-specific digital HR initiatives and the integration of analytics-driven decision-making to strengthen the aviation-tourism ecosystem.

Keywords: Digital HR; Aviation Industry; Tourism Development; Workforce Analytics; India

Comparative Analysis of AI-Driven and Automated HR Technologies for Sustainable Workforce Management, with Special Reference to the Aviation and Hotel Sectors of India

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Abstract

The transformation of human resource management through artificial intelligence and automation has significantly reshaped workforce systems across knowledge-driven industries. In India, the aviation and hospitality sectors operate in highly dynamic service environments where workforce sustainability, employee retention, productivity enhancement, and operational continuity are critical for long-term success. This study presents a comparative analytical examination of AI-driven and automated HR technologies in these sectors to evaluate their effectiveness in achieving sustainable workforce management. The research adopts an exploratory and analytical approach based on secondary data collected from academic journals, government reports, industry publications, and HR analytics studies. The analysis compares various HR technologies, including recruitment algorithms, predictive workforce planning systems, digital performance dashboards, automated payroll systems, chat-based engagement tools, and AI-enabled training platforms. The findings reveal that aviation organisations demonstrate higher technological integration in safety-related HR processes and predictive scheduling, while hotel enterprises show stronger adoption in talent acquisition, performance evaluation, and digital learning systems. The study proposes a sustainable AI-HR integration model that emphasises alignment between technological innovation, employee well-being, ethical data governance, and long-term workforce stability. Results indicate that AI-driven HR technologies contribute to improved efficiency, reduced recruitment cycle time, enhanced employee satisfaction, and sustainability through digitalisation. However, the study also highlights concerns related to skill displacement due to automation. The research offers policy-level recommendations for developing sector-specific HR digital frameworks to support sustainable workforce management in India's service economy.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; HR Automation; Workforce Sustainability; Aviation Industry India; Hotel Industry India

Reimagining Kanchipuram's Cultural Heritage: A Resident-Driven Narrative Framework for Sustainable Tourism Marketing

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Abstract

Kanchipuram is a living heritage city where cultural identity is expressed not only through monuments but also through everyday practices, rituals, craftsmanship, and community memory. Despite attracting a steady flow of pilgrims and cultural tourists, the representation of Kanchipuram in tourism marketing is largely shaped by institutional narratives and official promotional materials. These narratives often overlook the nuanced, lived experiences and perspectives of local residents. This study seeks to reposition these local voices at the center of cultural heritage marketing by developing a resident-driven narrative framework for sustainable tourism. The research focuses on key community stakeholders, including silk weavers, temple priests, women engaged in domestic and festival traditions, and elderly residents who hold intergenerational knowledge of the city's evolution. Using qualitative methods such as in-depth conversations, participant observation, and storytelling sessions, the study explores how these groups interpret their cultural heritage and what aspects they consider meaningful for visitors. Special attention is given to traditional weaving communities, whose contributions are widely recognized but seldom represented in their own voices within marketing discourse. By synthesizing these narratives, the study identifies common themes that inform a more inclusive and authentic approach to destination representation. The proposed framework emphasizes community participation, narrative authenticity, and cultural sensitivity in tourism promotion. The findings suggest that integrating resident perspectives can enhance the credibility and sustainability of heritage marketing while fostering cultural continuity. This research contributes to bridging the gap between tourism development and community identity, offering a model for more ethical and participatory heritage tourism practices.

Keywords: Resident-centered heritage marketing; Sustainable tourism; Cultural heritage; Kanchipuram heritage; Local storytelling

Influence of Brand Ambassadors over Consumer Decision Journey – A Phenomenal Study

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Abstract

Brand ambassadors play a vital role in promoting products and representing a company's identity in contemporary marketing environments. With increasing emphasis on customer-centric strategies, organizations invest significantly in celebrity endorsements to enhance brand visibility and influence consumer behavior. However, the effectiveness of such investments in generating returns and shaping customer loyalty remains a critical area of inquiry. This study examines the influence of brand ambassadors on the consumer decision journey, with a focus on their role in creating brand awareness and impacting purchase decisions. The research was conducted in Bengaluru city, a major urban and technological hub, using a descriptive research design. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire distributed to 625 respondents using convenience sampling, out of which 456 valid responses were analyzed. Statistical tools, including Chi-square tests and One-Way ANOVA, were employed to test hypotheses and assess relationships between variables. The findings reveal that a significant majority of respondents are brand-conscious and prefer purchasing branded products. It was observed that many of these products were promoted by brand ambassadors, particularly from the film industry. The results of the Chi-square tests indicate that brand ambassadors significantly contribute to creating awareness and have a strong influence on consumer purchase decisions. Furthermore, ANOVA results highlight that the degree of influence varies across age groups, with younger consumers being more strongly influenced than older segments. The study concludes that brand ambassadors hold a crucial position in shaping consumer buying behavior and brand perception. These findings provide valuable insights for marketers to strategically utilize brand ambassadors, particularly when targeting younger demographics, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of marketing campaigns and optimizing return on investment.

Keywords: Branding; Brand Ambassadors; Consumer Purchase Decision; Consumer Behavior; Celebrity Endorsement

Leveraging Block Chain for Green Bond Integrity: A Smart-Contract–Driven Model for Transparent and Fraud-Resilient Sustainable Finance

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Abstract

The rapid expansion of green bond markets has intensified concerns regarding the credibility of environmental reporting and post-issuance accountability. Although certification frameworks and ESG disclosure standards have improved initial screening processes, monitoring mechanisms remain largely documentation-based and periodic. This limitation creates potential risks related to reporting inconsistencies and reduced investor trust. This study proposes a governance-centered digital framework that integrates smart contract logic within a permissioned block chain environment to enable continuous, rule-based oversight across the lifecycle of green bonds. The research conceptualizes block chain not merely as a transparency tool but as programmable compliance infrastructure. The framework embeds key processes eligibility screening, allocation tracking, and environmental performance validation into executable smart contract logic. This enables real-time verification rather than retrospective auditing. The model is structured into three operational layers: eligibility structuring, allocation traceability, and performance validation, ensuring seamless lifecycle integration and enhanced governance. By aligning technological architecture with institutional requirements, the study addresses critical gaps in sustainable finance research, particularly the lack of lifecycle-integrated monitoring and limited focus on governance design. The framework reduces information asymmetry by minimizing reliance on issuer-driven disclosures and strengthens signaling credibility through automated compliance enforcement. The study concludes that embedding ESG criteria into programmable financial systems can significantly improve transparency, reduce verification costs, and enhance investor confidence. While implementation challenges such as regulatory coordination persist, the proposed model offers a robust pathway toward more resilient, accountable, and fraud-resistant sustainable finance ecosystem.

Keywords: Green bonds; Sustainable finance; Block chain; Smart contracts; Transparency; ESG governance

Analyzing the Critical Success Factors for Cost of Quality in Sustainable Manufacturing Systems: A BWM–GRA Combined Approach

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Abstract

In the contemporary manufacturing landscape, organizations face increasing pressure to minimize quality-related costs while maintaining sustainability and product excellence. Understanding the critical enablers that influence the cost of quality (CoQ) is essential for achieving operational efficiency and competitive advantage. This study focuses on identifying, evaluating, and prioritizing the key success factors that contribute to reducing CoQ in the Indian manufacturing sector using an integrated multi-criteria decision-making approach. The research employs Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) to rank CoQ enablers based on their relative importance, followed by validation using the Best Worst Method (BWM) and sensitivity analysis to ensure robustness of the findings. Data were collected from industry experts and academic professionals, and a comprehensive set of enablers was identified through literature review and empirical insights. The analysis reveals that employee training and education, top management commitment, operational manuals and worksheets, customer focus, and total preventive maintenance are among the most significant factors influencing CoQ reduction. The results indicate that inadequate training, lack of managerial support, and insufficient emphasis on customer requirements negatively impact quality performance and increase overall costs. The integrated GRA-BWM framework provides a systematic method for prioritizing these enablers, enabling organizations to allocate resources more effectively. This study contributes to sustainable manufacturing practices by offering actionable insights into quality management strategies that reduce waste, improve efficiency, and enhance organizational sustainability. The findings support decision-makers in developing targeted interventions to optimize quality costs while fostering long-term industrial growth.

Keywords: Cost of quality; Sustainable manufacturing; Grey relational analysis; Best worst method; Quality management; Decision-making

Implementing Sustainable Operations Practices to Reduce Carbon Footprint in the Textile Industry

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Abstract

The textile industry is recognized as one of the most carbon-intensive sectors due to energy-intensive processes such as dyeing, chemical treatment, and large-scale machinery operations. This study examines the implementation of sustainable operational practices aimed at reducing carbon footprints in textile manufacturing, with a focus on social, environmental, economic, and manufacturing dimensions. The research seeks to identify major emission sources, analyze existing sustainability practices, and evaluate their effectiveness in minimizing environmental impact. A structured research design was adopted using a purposive sample of 150 respondents from the textile industry. Data were collected through questionnaires capturing insights on emission sources, adoption of sustainable practices, and their perceived outcomes. Statistical analysis, including regression and hypothesis testing, was conducted to examine the relationship between sustainable operations and carbon footprint reduction. The findings indicate that dyeing and finishing processes are the most significant contributors to emissions, while energy-efficient technologies, renewable energy adoption, and waste management practices play a critical role in reducing carbon output. The results further reveal that social and environmental dimensions significantly influence sustainability outcomes, while economic practices contribute moderately to carbon reduction. Employee awareness, inclusivity, and organizational commitment emerged as key drivers of successful implementation. Additionally, sustainable practices were found to enhance organizational resilience, profitability, and environmental performance. The study concludes that integrating sustainable operational strategies across all functional dimensions can substantially reduce carbon emissions while promoting long-term economic and social benefits. It highlights the need for a holistic approach that aligns operational efficiency with environmental responsibility, thereby enabling the textile industry to transition toward a low-carbon and sustainable future.

Keywords: Textile industry; Carbon footprint; Sustainable operations; Energy efficiency; Green supply chain; Sustainability

From Place Distinctiveness to Tourism Support: The Role of Protecting and Supporting Behaviors of Meghalaya's Living Root Bridges Communities

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Abstract

Tourism development in rural destinations depends significantly on the support and participation of local communities. This study examines how residents' perception of place distinctiveness influences their voluntary behaviors and overall support for tourism, with specific reference to the Living Root Bridges communities in Meghalaya, India. Place distinctiveness, defined as the perceived uniqueness of a location, is explored as a key driver of community citizenship behavior, particularly protecting and supporting behaviors that contribute to sustainable tourism development. The research adopts a quantitative approach using a structured questionnaire administered to 152 residents from the villages of Tyrna and Nongriat. Established measurement scales were used to assess place distinctiveness, protecting behavior, supporting behavior, and support for tourism. Statistical techniques, including descriptive analysis, reliability testing, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analysis, were employed to test the hypothesized relationships. The findings reveal that place distinctiveness has a significant positive influence on both protecting and supporting behaviors among residents. In turn, these behaviors positively impact support for tourism, with supporting behavior showing a stronger effect compared to protecting behavior. The results indicate that when residents perceive their community as unique, they are more likely to engage in actions that preserve cultural and natural resources while actively supporting tourism initiatives. The study contributes to tourism literature by highlighting the role of place distinctiveness as a behavioral driver rather than merely an attitudinal factor. It also provides practical insights for policymakers and tourism planners to foster community engagement by strengthening residents' sense of uniqueness and encouraging participatory practices.

Keywords: Place distinctiveness; Community citizenship behavior; Protecting behavior; Supporting behavior; Tourism support; Sustainable tourism

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Best Practices in Sustainable Tourism: Case Studies from Japan, Singapore, Kerala, and Bhutan

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Abstract

Sustainable tourism has emerged as a global priority as destinations strive to balance economic growth with environmental protection and cultural preservation. This study examines best practices in sustainable tourism through four internationally recognized case studies: Japan, Singapore, Kerala, and Bhutan. Each destination demonstrates distinct approaches to sustainability shaped by governance structures, technological advancement, community involvement, and environmental priorities. The research adopts a qualitative comparative case study methodology based on secondary data sources, including academic literature, policy documents, and official tourism reports. A structured analytical framework is used to evaluate each case across four key dimensions: governance, technology, community involvement, and environmental outcomes. Japan demonstrates effective visitor management through disciplined cultural practices and digital crowd control systems. Singapore exemplifies smart tourism by integrating green infrastructure, real-time data systems, and efficient urban planning. Kerala highlights community-based tourism through initiatives such as Kudumbashree, promoting local empowerment and inclusive development. Bhutan adopts a value-based "High Value, Low Volume" tourism model, prioritizing environmental conservation and cultural integrity. The comparative analysis reveals that sustainable tourism does not follow a single universal model but varies based on socio-economic and institutional contexts. Technology-driven models enhance operational efficiency, while community-led approaches strengthen social sustainability and local ownership. Across all cases, strong governance, stakeholder coordination, and long-term planning emerge as critical success factors. The study contributes to the literature by integrating multiple dimensions of sustainable tourism into a unified framework. It offers practical insights for policymakers and tourism planners to design adaptive, inclusive, and resilient tourism strategies suited to diverse regional contexts.

Keywords: Sustainable tourism; Community-based tourism; Digital innovation; Tourism governance; Responsible tourism; Environmental sustainability

Electronic Word of Mouth in Digital Consumption Contexts: A Systematic Review of Drivers, Mechanisms, and Behavioral Outcomes

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Abstract

Electronic word of mouth (eWOM) has become a central informational input in consumer decision-making across digital platforms. Despite a rapidly expanding body of empirical research, findings remain fragmented across constructs, theoretical perspectives, and methodological approaches. This study presents a systematic review, guided by PRISMA 2020 protocols, synthesizing 47 peer-reviewed empirical studies that examine the influence of eWOM on consumer behavior. The review adopts a structured analytical framework encompassing four dimensions: eWOM attributes and message-level cues, contextual and platform conditions, underlying psychological and theoretical mechanisms, and behavioral outcomes. The findings indicate that the effectiveness of eWOM is primarily driven by information quality, credibility, and valence. These factors operate through key mediating mechanisms such as perceived usefulness, trust formation, and attitude development. Purchase intention emerges as the most frequently examined outcome, while evidence on long-term behavioral effects remains limited. The analysis also reveals methodological convergence, with a dominant reliance on cross-sectional survey designs and structural equation modeling, and comparatively limited use of longitudinal, qualitative, or behavioral data approaches. Theoretically, the literature reflects considerable diversity, with eWOM conceptualized variably as an informational stimulus, social influence mechanism, mediating construct, or behavioral outcome. By integrating fragmented findings and clarifying the distinct causal roles that eWOM assumes across empirical models, this review provides a consolidated understanding of its function within consumer behavior research. The study contributes to theory by delineating the boundaries of current empirical knowledge and offers directions for future research emphasizing methodological diversity, longitudinal analysis, and integrated theoretical frameworks.

Keywords: Electronic word of mouth (eWOM); Consumer behavior; Online reviews; Credibility and trust; Information usefulness; Purchase intention

Sustainable Impact of Real-Time Inventory Visibility on E-Commerce Customer Retention

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Abstract

Real-time inventory visibility (RTIV) has evolved from a purely operational tool into a strategic capability that significantly influences sustainability and customer retention in e-commerce. Frequent stock outs, inaccurate inventory records, and delayed restocking not only disrupt operations but also negatively impact customer satisfaction and loyalty. This study examines how RTIV enhances customer retention by improving operational responsiveness, reducing inefficiencies, and supporting sustainable business practices. The research focuses on the role of accurate and real-time stock information in minimizing order cancellations, reducing waste, and improving supply chain coordination. By ensuring transparency in product availability, organizations can align customer expectations with actual fulfillment performance, thereby strengthening trust and satisfaction. The study further explores how RTIV contributes to sustainability by reducing overproduction, minimizing unnecessary transportation, and lowering return rates caused by incorrect inventory information. Adopting a quantitative research approach, the study analyzes the relationship between RTIV and customer retention using statistical tools such as Chi-square tests and contingency analysis. The findings indicate a statistically significant relationship between real-time inventory visibility and customer retention. Additionally, customer satisfaction and operational responsiveness are identified as key mediating factors influencing this relationship. The results also highlight variations in retention behavior across demographic segments, particularly age groups, emphasizing the importance of targeted strategies. The study concludes that RTIV not only enhances operational efficiency but also acts as a driver of sustainable and customer-centric practices in e-commerce. By integrating real-time visibility with responsive supply chain management, businesses can achieve improved customer loyalty while contributing to environmental sustainability and long-term competitive advantage.

Keywords: Real-time inventory visibility; Customer retention; Sustainability; E-commerce operations; Supply chain responsiveness; Customer satisfaction

Circular Economy Branding and E-commerce Customer Retention: The Mediating Role of Product Lifecycle Communication and Return Operations Efficiency

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Abstract

The circular economy has emerged as a critical sustainability paradigm in the e-commerce sector, moving beyond regulatory compliance to influence customer engagement and long-term brand loyalty. However, persistent challenges such as high return rates, linear consumption patterns, and environmental degradation hinder the effective realization of sustainable value propositions and weaken consumer trust. This study examines how circular economy branding contributes to customer retention, with particular emphasis on the mediating roles of product lifecycle communication and return operations efficiency. The research explores how transparent communication regarding product sourcing, usage, return, and disposal enhances consumer understanding and reduces information asymmetry. Simultaneously, efficient return operations characterized by responsiveness, procedural simplicity, and operational reliability serve as a critical mechanism for reinforcing trust and satisfaction in the post-purchase phase. By integrating these elements, organizations can align sustainability initiatives with customer-centric strategies. Adopting a quantitative research design, the study utilizes factor analysis and regression techniques to examine relationships among circular economy mindset, branding, lifecycle communication, return efficiency, and customer retention. The findings reveal that circular economy branding significantly influences customer retention, with product lifecycle communication and return operations efficiency acting as key mediators. Among the variables, branding demonstrates the strongest impact, while communication and operational efficiency provide essential support in translating sustainability into tangible customer value. The study concludes that circular economy branding alone is insufficient without supporting operational and communicative mechanisms. Organizations must integrate transparent lifecycle communication and efficient reverse logistics processes to strengthen customer trust and loyalty. These insights offer practical implications for e-commerce firms seeking to balance sustainability objectives with long-term customer retention and competitive advantage.

Keywords: Circular economy branding; Product lifecycle communication; Return operations efficiency; Customer retention; E-commerce; Reverse logistics

Beyond Boundaries with Synergistic Alliances

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Abstract

In the modern digital setting, tourist businesses and destinations are much more inclined to attain sustainability, responsible travel and cooperative strategies to fulfil the needs of the changing consumers in terms of ethical and eco-friendly experiences. This paper is investigating the notion of Beyond Boundaries with Synergistic Alliances and how collaboration between companies, communities and digital platforms enhance sustainable marketing within and outside the bounds of borders. The aims of the paper are to comprehend the role of collaboration in sustainable tourism marketing, explore the way that online instruments can facilitate the responsible tourism alliances and determine what are the most important spheres where cooperation and collaboration between tourism stakeholders could be improved. The study has an extensive area of discussion both theoretically and practically on the issue of collaboration; value co-creation, boundary-spanning models and the relationships between public and private, as well as academic and industrial networks where structural, cultural and regional factors affecting the performance of alliances are discussed. It also examines the nature of operational tasks like knowledge sharing, integration of technology and pooling of resources and models of governance as well as the contribution of new forms of digital capabilities that support boundaryless cooperation. The anticipated results are that synergistic partnerships can largely ensure improved innovation, organizational health and competitive edge and allow tourism stakeholders to design meaningful and sustainable visitor experiences that cannot be developed by one single organization. The research concludes that digital tools such as data-driven planning tools and community engagement portals are at the core of driving to speed up the collaboration and responsible travel as well as suggesting such avenues as community participation, destination marketing and digital capacity building as a viable source of intensifying future partnerships.

Keywords: Synergistic alliances, sustainable marketing, responsible tourism, digital tools, collaboration, value co-creation, frameworks of cross-border partnerships, tourism stakeholders, innovation, cross-border partnerships.

A Study on Shadow Marketing and its Effect on Consumer Trust in Cosmetics

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Abstract

In the past few years, shadow marketing has been used more frequently in the cosmetics industry. This type of marketing is when an influencer markets a cosmetic product, without defining the sponsorship and advertising connection. As a hidden advertising channel, it raises concerns regarding the integrity of the influencer and the brand and how they are perceived by consumers. The main aim of study is to examine the role of shadow marketing influences on consumer trust and purchase intention, and if trust is a mediator of that effect, the study insights to measure both the direct and indirect effect of shadow marketing on consumer behaviour in the beauty category. Using a quantitative cross-sectional survey methodology, Data was gathered from 220 participants who are involved in the shadow marketing via survey 5-point scaled questionnaire using R software for reliability analysis, regression analysis to examine direct effects of shadow marketing, and trust to determine if they impacted the consumers' purchase intention. The outcome of the Reliability test Cronbach's alpha: shadow marketing ($\alpha = 0.86$), trust ($\alpha = 0.88$), and purchase intention ($\alpha = 0.84$). which indicates strong consistency of the data, and also analysed descriptive statistics it indicates consumers have moderate exposure ($M = 3.41$, $SD = 0.74$) to shadow marketing and little trust in influencers using shadow marketing ($M = 2.78$, $SD = 0.81$), and moderate purchase intentions ($M = 3.12$, $SD = 0.69$). Challenging statistical assumptions indicated a large level of reliability for all the constructs. The results of the regression analyses indicates that shadow marketing has negative impact on consumer trust ($\beta = -0.54$, $p < 0.001$), and also negatively impacts purchase intention ($\beta = -0.29$, $p < 0.01$). Trust has a positive effect on purchase intention ($\beta = 0.47$, $p < 0.001$). The mediation analysis says that shadow marketing has an indirect effect on purchase intention through trust ($\beta_{\text{indirect}} = -0.25$, 95% CI [-0.34, -0.17]), indicating a partial mediation. The proposed model gives 51% of the variance in purchase intention ($R^2 = 0.51$), with an overall correlation of $R = 0.71$. The study concluded that shadow marketing has a negative influence on consumers' trust and purchase behaviour.

Keywords: Shadow marketing, influencer marketing, consumer trust, purchase intention, cosmetics industry, consumer behaviour.

The Effectiveness of Guerrilla Marketing in Digital Era: A Study of Consumer Awareness, Attitudes and Purchase Intention

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Abstract

The traditional advertisement is always centred on competitive marketplace consumers in an ever-evolving digital world and brands are growing up. One of the traditional types is the guerrilla marketing. Guerrilla marketing is augmenting brand care and ingenious strategic reaction and predetermined growth patterns and kindle growth of audience engagement. The real effects of consumer consciousness and purchase decision attitudes are yet not mentioned well. Little has been done to do an in-depth study on the decision making of consumers. The primary objective of the research is to analyse the effects of guerrilla marketing on the environment and the effect on the consumer awareness, attitudes, and purchase intentions as well involved. The article utilized qualitative and quantitative designs whereby 5-point structured questionnaire survey was used on digitally activated consumers and yielded 250 valid responses. Conducted and analysed the R software Regression analysis performed and considered the effects of awareness and attitude on purchase intention. The study finding is that guerrilla marketing is identified to increase the brand recall and has a positive influence on the consumer perceptions. Nevertheless, R-values are explained strongly ($R = 0.79$, $R^2 = 0.62$) and both awareness ($\beta = 0.31$, $p < 0.01$) and attitudes ($\beta = 0.38$, $p < 0.001$) had a significant effect on purchase intention. The findings indicate that consumer purchase intention is highly determined by guerrilla marketing, and the model accounts to 62% of the consumer purchase intention. Awareness ($\beta = 0.31$) and attitudes ($\beta = 0.38$) have a significant and positive influence on purchase intention. The study found out that the incorporation of value-based effect of trust augmenting the communication is required effect of the transformation of the engagement as the party that makes the consumer decisions.

Keywords: Guerrilla Marketing, Purchase Intension, Brand Awareness, Attention

From Waste to Value: How Circular Branding Transforms Modern Retail

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Abstract

The growing concerns surrounding environmental degradation, resource scarcity, carbon emissions, and global waste accumulation have compelled modern retailers to shift from traditional linear consumption models toward circular economy-oriented practices. Retail sectors such as fashion, electronics, and home goods are increasingly adopting initiatives such as recycling, repair, refurbishment, resale, take-back systems, and sustainable packaging. However, operational circularity alone is insufficient unless it is communicated credibly and converted into meaningful brand value. This study examines how circular branding enables retailers to reposition waste as a source of economic, environmental, and symbolic value. Using a qualitative secondary data-based content analysis, the study analyses publicly available sustainability reports, corporate disclosures, official websites, campaign materials, ESG documents, press releases, and brand communication practices of selected retail brands. The research focuses on how circular economy principles are embedded into brand identity, marketing communication, and customer experience across fashion, electronics, and home goods sectors. The findings reveal three dominant strategic patterns: waste-to-value framing, authenticity signalling, and trust-based competitive differentiation. Retailers communicate circularity through measurable sustainability metrics, lifecycle disclosures, third-party certifications, repair and resale platforms, and consumer participation mechanisms. The study further indicates that trust acts as a central mechanism linking circular branding with brand equity and long-term competitive advantage. Circular branding helps transform sustainability from a compliance-driven activity into a strategic value proposition that enhances consumer confidence, market differentiation, and stakeholder legitimacy. The study contributes to sustainability branding and circular economy literature by demonstrating how branding functions as a bridge between internal sustainability practices and external consumer perception in modern retail markets.

Keywords: Circular Branding; Circular Economy; Sustainable Retail; Waste-to-Value; Sustainability Communication; Secondary Data Analysis

The Green Mirage in Tourism: Effects on Purchase Intentions through Trust, Image, and Environmental Concern

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Abstract

The present paper examines how greenwashing in tourism influences the buying intentions of the tourists through the mediating effects of green trust and destination image, and the moderating influence of environmental concern. As competition intensifies in the sustainable tourism industry, various service providers such as ecofriendly spots, eco-hotels, airlines, and resorts are making environmental claims that are mostly deceptive and present a threat of greenwashing. 712 tourists who were exposed to sustainability-based travel promotions were used as subjects of the data collection, and the hypothesized model was evaluated with the help of the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). The findings indicate that the perceived greenwashing has a deleterious impact on trust of tourists as well as destination image that have a significant influence on the purchase intentions. More so, environmental concern moderates these relations, mitigating the adverse effect of greenwashing to highly environmentally-friendly travellers. The results also demonstrate the relevance of genuine and open sustainability communication in the tourism sector and adds to the body of knowledge by incorporating the consumer perceptions of the digital era into the greenwashing-tourism paradigm.

Keywords: Greenwashing, Tourism, Green Trust, Destination Image, Environmental Concern.

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Sustainability-Infused Core Brand Attributes and Its Impact on Purchase Intentions

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Abstract

This research explores how the attributes of core brands that are infused with the sustainability concept affect the consumer purchase intention with 492 respondents. It re-conceptualizes quality, reliability, performance, innovation, and reputation in a sustainability framework, and re-model them as a higher-order construct. The results of the analysis conducted through the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) show that all attributes have a significant impact on the purchase intention with the strongest predictor being the sustainable brand reputation and performance has a moderate impact. Notably, Consumer Perception of Sustainability is a key mediating factor, greatly determining the process of decoding and translating sustainability cues into buy intentions. The overall impact of higher-order construct is also strong, which supports the overall effect of these attributes. This work adds value as it provides a comprehensive and empirically tested framework that deals with divided research, and emphasizes the importance of the consumer perception in boosting the efficiency of the sustainability-oriented brand approaches.

Keywords: Sustainability, Brand Attributes, Sustainable Brand Quality, Sustainable Innovation, Brand Reputation, Purchase Intentions and Consumer Behaviour.

Sustainable Brand Signals and Economic Competitiveness: A Consumer-Centric Study in Emerging Markets

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Abstract

This paper studies the effect of sustainable brand signals on consumers perceptions of economic competitiveness in the emerging markets where there is a co-existence of sustainability expectations and high price sensitivity. Based on the research on 512 respondents, the study compares the effect of green brand image, green trust, perceived economic value, green product quality and sustainable communication effectiveness on perceived competitive advantage. The proposed relationships were tested using the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). The findings suggest that the overall impact of all the sustainable brand signals on perceived economic competitiveness is significant and green trust and perceived economic value are the strongest predictors. Moreover, through mediation analysis, it is indicated that the green trust and perceived economic value mediate the key relationships to some extent, and therefore they are important in conveying the sustainability cues to competitive performance. The model has high explanatory power, which shows that sustainability-driven perceptions play a major role in competitiveness. The results indicate that consumers in the new markets are becoming conscious of sustainability in terms of credibility as well as the economics, which provides a strategic direction to companies interested in creating competitive advantage.

Keywords: Sustainable brand signals, economic competitiveness, consumer perceptions, emerging markets, PLS-SEM.

Driving Sustainable Purchase Intentions via the AARRR Growth Funnel: Consumer Market Evidences

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Abstract

The role of sustainable in consumer decision-making is becoming more focal but the processes by which growth measures affect sustainable purchase intentions are under-investigated. In this study, the independent variables that are used are the AARRR framework, Acquisition, Activation, Retention, Referral and Revenue, which directly affect Sustainable Purchase Intention.. A systematic survey was conducted among 501 participants in sustainable consumer markets, and all the AARR steps were operationalized by the questionnaire that evaluated product discovery and initial engagement and long-term use and referral behaviors as well as the perceived financial value. The analysis was conducted based on the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) to reveal the significance and strength of the relationships among each of the growth stages and the sustainable purchase intention. Findings indicate that the five AARRR stages have a positive and significant effect on the intentions of consumers to buy sustainable products. It is important to point out that the effects of Retention and Referral, in turn, are the strongest ones and indicate the significance of further interaction and advocacy in encouraging the environmentally friendly behavior. The results derived are practical to the marketer interested in incorporating sustainability in the management of customer lifecycle to highlight that growth strategies that are organized can serve as an effective method of pursuing sustainable consumption and business performance.

Keywords: Sustainable purchase intention, AARRR model, Sustainable consumer behavior, PLS-SEM, Growth funnel.

Balancing Sustainable Tourism with Economy: A Study for Tourism Taxation from Indian Context

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Abstract

Tourism is an important revenue generating activity for any economy. Sustainable tourism is an important type of tourism that is primarily important for conserving the environment and nature. Tourism involve developing the picturesque spots in a sustainable way and by Taxing the tourist's public revenue generation is also addressed. This paper offers a comprehensive study of the current practices for the Indirect Taxes levied by the government and the level of stakeholder's acceptance. The objective of this study is to determine the amounts of taxes and/or public fees that tourists appear to be more willing to pay in order to improve the sustainability and experience of the mature tourism destination. Our paper also tries to identify the reasons where the tourists are willing to pay more for the overall development of the picturesque spots in India.

Key Words: Sustainable Tourism, Tourists, Indirect Taxes, India, Economy, Picturesque Spots, Revenue Generation, taxation.

Digital Marketing as a Driver for Sustainable Tourism Development

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Abstract

Digital marketing is a significant instrument for promoting responsible tourism by leveraging multiple online platforms to promote sustainability, influence traveler behavior, and boost economic growth. Content marketing, social media, search engines, and VR/AR experiences are examples of strategies that can emphasize a destination's sustainable offers, promote responsible customer behavior, and increase awareness of environmental and social issues. But it's also critical to deal with issues like "greenwashing," and to work with stakeholders to make sure marketing initiatives actually promote the growth of sustainable tourism.

Digital marketing is the promotion of products and services using electronic devices and digital channels, such as the internet, social media, and mobile phones. It has transformed traditional marketing by enabling businesses to reach target audiences globally through data-driven strategies, including SEO, content marketing, social media, and email. This approach allows for more personalized, cost-effective, and measurable campaigns, though it also presents challenges due to the rapid pace of technological change and the need to capture consumer attention.

Keywords: Responsible Tourism, Social Media, Measurable Campaigns, Digitalization, Cost Effective

The Role of Agritourism in Strengthening Rural Resilience and Sustainable Livelihoods

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Abstract

Agritourism has become a significant policy to rural development and diversification of livelihoods in most countries, including India. Agritourism gives farmers a chance to earn extra revenue and to stop the reliance on traditional agricultural activities only. This paper discusses the development and significance of agrotourism and how it enhances rural resilience as well as sustainable livelihoods. It is a secondary research that was conducted using secondary data such as government reports, research papers, and published documents covering agritourism development in India. The objective of the analysis is the growth of agritourism, patterns of state-wise development, as well as its role in diversifying livelihoods of rural people by generating income, creating jobs, and promoting rural entrepreneurship. The results indicate that agritourism could considerably contribute to the economic sustainability of rural regions by introducing alternative sources of income and publicity of tourism activities in the farms. Its growth can however be challenged by low infrastructure, ignorance of farmers, and institutional lack of support. More enhancement of agritourism can also be done through strengthening of policy support, rural infrastructure and offering of training to farmers. On the whole, agritourism may become a sustainable way of rural development in such aspects as the diversification of livelihoods, maintenance of the rural culture, and resilience of the farming communities.

Keywords: Agritourism, Responsible tourism, Rural Resilience, Sustainable Development, Tourism Development.

Adoption of Technology in Tourist Attraction: A Case Study On Impact of IOT and Apps with Special Reference to Shri Kshetra Ganagapur Dattatreya

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Abstract

The Indian economy is elevating on to a greater level courtesy of tourism industry and retaining the most significant portion of GDP expansion. Tourism industry is luring tourists at a bigger pace with each passing second due to its culture and heritages. The research centralizes on the role of a technology in planning and enhancing the tourism business. AI is the technology that collects all the data and displays it to the end users in one platform as it translation of the hard work to the easy part in collecting the data on a place or attractions, which exists online. With the internet the current generation are accustomed to the internet and research on the destination of their travels before the actual flight. By this, considering it as a significant fact, Internet of Things (IOT) of a destination influence much and introduce numerous alterations in the development of the destination and the inflow of tourists. The information regarding the destination is gathered by the visitors in the pre-planning and on the trip. As they receive the information on the fingertip, it makes the life of everyone easy to live in this present generation. In cases when the information is released or is released by official websites or apps are more reliable than other source of information on any place. In this paper, we shall learn about how visitors or tourists become familiar to the Internet technology and how it assists in pre-planning and during the trip to achieve the satisfactory level and experience of trip according to their expectations.

Keywords: Tourism Attraction, Technology, Artificial intelligence, social media, Tourist behavior, Internet of Things (IOT), Apps.

Digital Finance and Sustainable Financial Capability: Opportunities and Risks for Gen Z in India

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Abstract

Digital finance platforms have quietly but fundamentally changed how young people handle money. Yet for all the attention these platforms receive, we still know surprisingly little about whether they actually help users build lasting financial capability. This study takes a closer look at that question, focusing specifically on how nudge mechanisms built into digital platforms interact with financial self-regulation to shape long-term financial well-being among Gen Z users (aged 21–29) living in Indian metropolitan cities. Drawing on nudge theory and financial self-regulation theory, the research explores how the design choices embedded in everyday apps systematically push users toward certain behaviours and what that means for their financial futures. Survey data from 127 respondents, analysed through correlation methods, produced some genuinely surprising results. Nearly everyone in the sample used UPI regularly ($M = 4.67$), yet payment platform usage had almost no relationship with financial capability ($r = 0.026$). Simply having access to digital payments, it turns out, does not make someone financially capable. What did matter and by a wide margin was financial self-regulation ($r = 0.657$, $p < .001$). People who planned ahead, saved consistently, and resisted impulse purchases scored dramatically higher on financial capability than those who did not. Platform nudges created a real tension: 72.4% of respondents openly acknowledged that frictionless payments pushed them to spend more than they intended, yet that awareness did little to change their actual behaviour. The central takeaway is that the path from digital finance to genuine financial capability runs through behavioural discipline, not through access or financial knowledge alone. These findings carry practical implications for educators, app designers, and policymakers who want digital finance to genuinely serve young users rather than quietly work against them.

Keywords: Nudge theory, financial self-regulation, digital finance, sustainable financial capability, Gen Z

Assessing Greenwashing Practices in FMCG: Consumer Challenges and Segmental Variations

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Abstract

Greenwashing has become a particularly hot topic in the FMCG world where irresponsible labelling around sustainability erodes consumers' confidence. It attempts to fulfil two objectives: mediating effect of greenwashing with problems encountered by green consumers, and variation in prevalence of greenwashing over the different FMCG categories. A purposive sampling of 390 respondents was analysed by Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA), Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA). ANOVA results indicated significant differences across product segments for most dimensions of greenwashing – Sin of Vagueness, Lesser of Two Evils, Hidden Trade-off, Irrelevance and Worshipping False Labels – with Health Care Products consistently scoring the highest. Conversely, there were no differences in Sin of Fibbing and Sin of No Proof, with MANOVA detecting no overall multivariate difference. CCA showed a statistically significant yet weak pair-wise link between greenwashing and the consumer test. Such 'greenwashing' is found to differ within the FMCG categories, specifically health-related ones; and even when weakly related it has detrimental effects on consumer trust, reinforcing the necessity of more stringent regulation and transparent communication.

Keywords: Greenwashing, FMCG sector, Consumer challenges, ANOVA, Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA), Sustainability

Crafting Resilient Business Model for Sustainability of Future Startups: Insights from Bengaluru's Successes and Failures

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Abstract

Bengaluru hosts 13,448 DPIIT-recognized startups (January 2025 Factbook), comprising over 80% of Karnataka's 16,600 total startups. India's tech startup ecosystem ranks 4th globally as of November 2025, with Bengaluru and NCR accounting for over 50% of national startups mentioned in GSER (Global Startup Ecosystem Report) 2025 by Startup Genome. Yet, intense competition, infrastructure deficits, regulatory hurdles, high living costs, and unforeseen expenses contribute to high startup mortality rates, despite abundant government schemes and rising unicorns. This failure erodes investor confidence, impacts entrepreneurs, jobs, and the economy, underscoring the need for targeted sustainability strategies. Researchers had made a humble attempt to develop a business model for studying the failure rates of Bengaluru startups. This study examines Bengaluru's startup ecosystem, identifying success and failure factors through primary data from 800 founders as a sample of both technology and non- technology startups. It proposes a Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) framework, validated via Fornell-Larcker criterion, with 12 constructs. Independent variables Marketing Orientation, Network, Resource, and Institutional Support directly influence Business Sustainability (the dependent variable reflecting survival rates). Critical Success Factors mediate these relationships, while Business Incubators moderate them, offering Multifaceted understanding into direct, indirect, and conditional effects. Grounded in peer-reviewed literature and practitioner views, the model equips budding entrepreneurs with resilient strategies. Findings benefit founders, teams, investors, employees, consumers, accelerators, incubators, academic institutions, students, and scholars pursuing further research on startup viability.

Keywords: Startup failure factors, resilient strategies, business model, sustainability, critical success factors.

Responsible Tourism Practices: An empirical Study of Tirumala Tirupati Devasthanams (TTD) with respect to pilgrim satisfaction towards services

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Abstract

Religious tourism is considered as an important part of cultural and spiritual economy of India and Tirumala has become one of the most visited pilgrimage sites in the world. The administrative challenge of controlling the high number of pilgrims coming to the country and maintaining the sanctity and quality of the services is a big problem. Pilgrim satisfaction in the religious institutions is affected by the interplay of the emotional, ritualistic, devotional and operational dimensions unlike in the conventional service sectors. This paper is an empirical research investigating pilgrim satisfaction to service offered at Tirumala Tirupati Devasthanams (TTD). A total of 65 pilgrims were interviewed using a structured questionnaire on ten dimensions of services, such as welfare services, safety, staff behaviour, ritual services, information dissemination, and waiting time of the Darshan, to obtain primary data. The descriptive statistics, reliability analysis, Pearson correlation and multiple regression techniques were used. These findings indicate that Darshan (Mean = 4.66), Safety and Security (Mean = 4.63), and Laddu Prasadam (Mean = 4.63) have a high level of satisfaction and Waiting Time (Mean = 2.63) was the major cause of dissatisfaction. The tool showed a high degree of internal consistency (Cronbach 88). The results of the regression analysis reveal that Safety, Laddu Prasadam, Staff Behaviour, Information Dissemination, and Free Meals have a positive impact on Darshan satisfaction, but Waiting Time has a negative effect on it ($\beta = -0.31$, $p < 0.01$). The 66 percent variance in the satisfaction of Darshan is explained by the model ($R^2 = 0.66$). The research paper is relevant to literature in the field of religious tourism and service quality by identifying the multidimensional and interdependent character of pilgrim satisfaction and providing practical implications of overall pilgrim experience improvement.

Keywords: Religious Tourism; Pilgrim Satisfaction; Darshan Experience; Service Quality; Welfare Services; Waiting Time Management; Safety and Security; Ritual Services; Multiple Regression Analysis; Tirumala Tirupati Devasthanams (TTD).

Eco Tourism Model in Wildlife Sanctuary for Socio-Economic Development of Backward Region - A Study of Chincholi Wildlife Sanctuaty

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Abstract

The Scholarly research paper examines ecotourism as a model of administering socio-economic growth and environmental preservation in the retrogressive areas, the Chincholi Wildlife Sanctuary in Karnataka. Chincholi is the first dry land sanctuary in south India where it is offering livelihood to the people, a platform to engage in community work and the protection of the biodiversity. This study is based on Eco tourists using five-point Likert scale parameters reveal the positive influence of ecotourism in the sphere of employment, income, and environmental awareness. This study finds that ecotourism Practices with community engagement shall improve sustainability. Economic sustainability emerged as a key driver for the success of ecotourism initiatives. The development of tourism-related infrastructure, promotion of local handicrafts, and creation of employment opportunities in guiding, hospitality, and transport services contribute to increased income levels and reduced migration. The study highlights that when local communities derive tangible economic benefits from ecotourism, their support for conservation initiatives significantly improves. By aligning conservation goals with community development, ecotourism can serve as a powerful tool for inclusive growth. The study contributes to the existing literature by providing a context-specific framework that can be replicated in similar ecologically sensitive and economically disadvantaged regions.

Keywords: Sustainable development, Community participation, Ecotourism, Chincholi Wildlife Sanctuary and biodiversity protection

Startup Funding Challenges for Nascent Entrepreneurs: A Case Study on Mashaw Sales Corporation

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Abstract

The Oil and Gas sector plays a crucial role in supporting industrial, commercial, and hospitality development, with liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) systems forming an essential component of safe and efficient energy distribution. Similar to other infrastructure-intensive industries, the LPG pipeline and LOT installation sector requires substantial capital investment for equipment procurement, safety compliance, and project execution (Kumar et al., 2020). Funding thus becomes a critical determinant of business sustainability and long term growth. According to Barot (2015), entrepreneurs face multiple challenges, beginning with risk-bearing at the start-up stage, followed by managing uncertainty, market volatility, and financial obligations as the business grows. Entrepreneurship, often viewed as a form of self-employment, demands continuous engagement and proactive decision-making. This study aims to examine the funding landscape, funding combinations, and challenges faced by start-ups in Hubballi and Dharwad with special reference to Mashaw Sales Corporation, a firm engaged in Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) pipeline installation and LOT installation. The study focuses on understanding the role of personal savings, family funds, and bank loans in sustaining business operations, as well as the influence of external and internal factors on funding decisions. A case study methodology was adopted to enable an in-depth exploration of real-life funding practices within the firm (Stake, 1995). Thematic analysis was employed to identify, analyze, and interpret recurring patterns related to funding sources, utilization, challenges, and outcomes (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The findings reveal that a combination of personal savings, family funds, and bank loans played a vital role in ensuring financial stability and business continuity. While these funding alternatives supported business expansion and liquidity, challenges such as delayed client payments, high interest rates, extensive documentation, and rigid repayment schedules posed significant constraints. The study concludes that although mixed funding strategies reduce dependency on a single source, effective cash flow management and supportive financial institutions are essential for long-term sustainability in capital-intensive sectors.

Keywords: Startup Finance, Funding Challenges, Case Study Approach, LPG Infrastructure Business, Financial Sustainability.

Startup Funding Challenges in North Karnataka: A Case Study on Pearl Builders and Developers

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Abstract

The real estate sector is a vital component of the global economy, anticipated to reach a market size of \$5,852.02 billion by 2030, with a compound annual growth rate of 6.2% from 2025 to 2030 (Grand View Research, 2024). The industry includes diverse activities such as property development, sales, rentals, and management (Kumar et al., 2020). Residential property commands a significant market share, accounting for 35.33% of revenue in 2024 (Grand View Research, 2024). Commercial real estate, encompassing office structures and retail establishments, constitutes another vital sector (Wurzbach, 2020). Real estate investment trusts (REITs) offer individuals an opportunity to invest in real estate without the necessity of directly managing properties (Chan et al., 2019). Funding is the backbone for any business survival. Funding sources varies depending on the types of business and size of business. According to Barot (2015), an entrepreneur must first take on the risk of starting a business, then deal with the uncertainty and volatility of the industry, particularly for those who launch a business for the first time, and finally make money. Identifying entrepreneurship as a form of "self-employment" is the most straightforward way to comprehend its meaning. Furthermore, an entrepreneur is "Never being in a state of doing nothing,"accordingtoBell,2009). The objective of the paper is to explore the funding landscape and alternatives in North Karnataka's real estate business with special reference to Pearl Builders and Developers. Case Study methodology approach was used as it involves exploration and detailed understanding of a phenomenon within its real-life context (Stake, 1995). Thematic analysis was used to identify, analyze, and interpret patterns and themes in qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The major finding was Family and friends, personal savings and loans provided financial sustenance and survival for the business. The irregularity in repayment schedules from customers was a major hurdle for the business and its repayment for the financial external liabilities.

Keywords: Funding Challenges, case study, funding alternatives and sustenance.

Educating Online Consumers for Sustainability: Impact on Shopping Experiences and Repurchase Intentions

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Abstract

Consumer education on sustainability plays a very important role in achieving the sustainability goals of the country. In emerging online markets, it plays a crucial role in promoting eco-friendly and responsible consumption. Such education enables consumers to make informed decisions that are beneficial to businesses, consumers, and the planet. Despite its importance, limited studies have examined how different dimensions of consumer education on sustainability influence online customer shopping experience and repurchase intention and also the mediating role of online customer shopping experience in this relationship. The present study addresses this gap by building a conceptual model to study consumer education on sustainability and its impact on shopping experiences and repurchase intentions by integrating Stimulus-Organism-Response theory. The data was collected from 231 online shoppers through a structured questionnaire. Convenience sampling technique was used for the study. Consumer Education on Sustainability was measured through sustainability awareness, information quality, transparency and disclosure, and eco-label understanding. The proposed model was tested using Structural Equation Modeling to validate the hypothesized relationships. The findings reveal that information quality and eco-label understanding significantly enhance online customers shopping experience which in turn strongly influence repurchase intention. However, sustainability awareness and transparency and disclosure do not show a significant impact on online customer shopping experience. The results demonstrate acceptable reliability, validity, and model fit. The study contributes to e-commerce and sustainability literature and offers practical guidance to e-retailers in designing effective educational content to promote responsible consumption and foster long term sustainability.

Keywords: Consumer Education, Sustainability, Online Customer Shopping Experiences, Repurchase Intention, Structural Equation Modeling

AI-Driven Recruitment and Selection as a Sustainable Digital HR Practice: An Ensemble Model Perspective from Indian Firms

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Abstract

The accelerated development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is changing organizational practices, and in particular, human resource management, through recruitment and selection, which is one of the major drivers of a robust workforce. While the usage of AI tools in recruitment has become widespread in organizations, the study found no prior empirical research on the success of the advanced AI models, specifically the ensemble learning models and their roles in sustainable human resource practices in Indian organizations. A mixed-method research design was employed to collect data on 352 HR managers, recruiters, and HR analytics professionals in Indian companies to test the relationships between organizational AI readiness, AI adoption, ensemble model performance, recruitment effectiveness, and sustainable HR outcomes using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). At the same time, we applied ensemble learning to recruitment-related data to compare the predictive accuracy of these methods with the alternative individual models of machine learning. The results indicate that organizational readiness is a significant predictor for AI adoption in recruitment, and the performance of the ensemble models is superior to the standalone models in terms of accuracy, consistency, and bias reduction. The findings also reveal that AI-based recruitment is effective and contributes to a fair decision-making process and long-term stability and sustainability of the workforce.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Recruitment and Selection, Ensemble Models, Sustainable HR Practices, Digital Transformation, Indian Firms.

The Impact of Cryptocurrency on India's Financial Ecosystem: Evidence from Urban Users on Opportunities, Risks, and Regulatory Clarity

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Abstract

The growing popularity of cryptocurrency has transformed the world's financial framework by introducing decentralized systems for value transfer, investment, and financial participation. The growing adoption of crypto and the digital penetration of emerging economies such as India have sparked interest among the masses, but the fear of volatility and investor security and regulatory uncertainty continue to shape the behaviour of adopters. This paper explores the impact of cryptocurrency on the Indian financial ecosystem by examining the impact on perceived benefits, perceived risks and regulatory clarity of the intention to adopt the currency. The study adopts a quantitative survey-based research design using primary data collected from 365 respondents across four urban regions. Key constructs were measured using a structured questionnaire with five-point Likert scale questions. Data analysis was performed by means of descriptive statistics, reliability and correlation analysis, and multiple regression. The results show that respondents consider that cryptocurrency is a relatively useful financial innovation, increasing efficiency and availability at global level, but that there are also important risks, including volatility and security issues, that respondents need to consider. It was found that regulatory clarity has a critical impact on the intention to adopt. These findings suggest that a balanced regulatory framework is needed to facilitate the uptake of crypto in the Indian financial system, while at the same time facilitating innovation and protecting consumers. This research adds empirical data to the small body of research on the uptake of crypto in non-industrialised countries and presents policy implications for regulators and financial institutions.

Keywords: Cryptocurrency Adoption; Perceived Benefits; Perceived Risks; Regulatory Clarity; Financial Innovation; India

Enhancing KPA with AI on the EI in the Tourism Sector

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Abstract

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) with Emotional Intelligence (EI) is increasingly transforming organizational performance, particularly in service-intensive industries such as tourism. As AI systems evolve to simulate human-like interactions, their ability to recognize and respond to emotional cues has significant implications for Key Performance Areas (KPA) of employees. This study examines the influence of AI on EI and its subsequent impact on employee performance within the tourism sector. A descriptive and quantitative research design was adopted, with data collected from 204 employees working in tourism-related organizations across Karnataka. A structured questionnaire using a five-point Likert scale was employed to measure the constructs of AI, EI, and KPA. Statistical techniques including descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analysis were used to evaluate relationships among variables. Reliability and factor analysis confirmed the consistency and validity of the measurement scales.

The findings indicate that AI has a significant positive influence on EI, and both AI and EI significantly impact KPA. The results further reveal that EI acts as a mediating factor through which AI enhances employee performance. The regression analysis demonstrates that a substantial proportion of variance in KPA is explained by AI and EI, highlighting their combined importance in improving workplace effectiveness. The study concludes that the adoption of AI-driven tools, when integrated with emotional intelligence capabilities, can enhance employee productivity, service quality, and customer satisfaction in the tourism industry. The research offers practical implications for organizations to leverage AI technologies while fostering emotional competencies among employees. It also contributes to the growing body of knowledge on the intersection of AI, human behavior, and performance outcomes in emerging service economies.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence, Key Performance Area, Tourism

Digital-Era Leadership: The Impact of Women Transformational Leadership on Team Effectiveness and Organisational Success

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Abstract

Leadership performance becomes especially important in the modern digital business world to foster team operations and improve organisational performance outcomes. The paper investigates the effectiveness of transformational leadership by women in organisations and team effectiveness is the mediating factor in this study. Quantitative research design was used and the primary data came out of 530 corporate workers in various sectors of the industry. Regression analysis and partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) were the methods of analysis of the proposed relationships. The empirical evidence demonstrates that the positive variance of women transformational leadership on team effectiveness and organisational success is strong and statistically significant. It was also revealed that the team effectiveness is a significant predictor of organisational success and thus the contribution of team functioning towards the attainment of organisational performance goals is eminent. The mediation analysis showed also that team effectiveness is one of the mediators that mediate the effects of leadership and organisational success, thus, leadership impacts not only directly but also indirectly on the organisational performance through improved team processes. The research will be relevant to the work on leadership and organisational behaviour by offering empirical evidence that the strategic value of transformational leadership practices among women leaders in digitally transforming corporate settings. The results provide viable recommendations to organisations that would want to enhance leadership development programmes, team work, and organisational effectiveness in the long term.

Keywords: Women Transformational Leadership; Team Effectiveness; Organisational Success; Digital Workplace; Leadership Diversity; Structural Equation Modelling

Sustainable Brand Positioning: A Systematic Review of Strategies, Consumer Perceptions, and Digital Engagement

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Abstract

The growing importance of sustainability has prompted brands to reconsider their positioning strategies in response to changing consumer expectations and increasing digitalization. The scope of this review covers research on sustainable brand positioning, focusing on sustainability-oriented brand strategies, consumer perceptions, and digital engagement practices. This study adopts a systematic literature review methodology, synthesizing peer-reviewed journal articles selected and analyzed using thematic analysis. The review consolidates fragmented literature and identifies dominant strategic approaches, key consumer perception outcomes such as trust and authenticity, and the role of digital platforms in communicating sustainability. The study contributes to the literature by offering a structured synthesis of sustainable brand positioning research and by identifying key research gaps and future research directions. The findings provide valuable insights for both scholars and practitioners aiming to develop credible and effective sustainable brand positioning in an increasingly digital marketplace.

Keywords: Sustainable brand positioning, consumer perception, digital engagement, systematic literature review

Integrating Personalized Product Recommendations in Omnichannel Strategies for Sustainable Digital Marketing in B2C Tourism Market

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Abstract

The rapid growth of Business-to-consumer tourism industry has strengthened the need for effective and sustainable digital marketing strategies. Integrating personalized product recommendations within omnichannel frameworks has emerged as a key approach to enhance the customer experience while improving marketing efficiency. This study explores the effectiveness of personalized product recommendations in enhancing customer engagement, ensuring cross-channel consistency in B2C tourism market. This study adopts an omnichannel perspective to examine how data-driven personalization across online and offline touchpoints reduces marketing inefficiencies and improves decision-making. It also investigates implementation challenges related to data collection, real-time integration and data privacy concerns. A quantitative research methodology was employed using structured questionnaires to analyse factors influencing the acceptance and effectiveness of personalized recommendations. The findings aim to provide practical insights for tourism industry's marketers on how the omnichannel personalization improves overall customer satisfaction, marketing performance and conversions while contributing to sustainable digital marketing strategies by minimizing inefficient promotional efforts.

Keywords: Business-to-Consumer, Digital Marketing, Omnichannel Strategy, Personalized Product Recommendations, Sustainable, Tourism market.

Purchase Readiness toward Green Products among Young Consumers

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Abstract

The shift toward sustainable consumption is vital for achieving environmental goals in emerging economies where young consumers signify a substantial market segment. Students as future opinion leaders play a key role in determining green consumption patterns. The current study examines the readiness of Indian scholars to purchase green products by exploring their stages of environmental awareness, attitudes toward sustainability and purchase intentions. By means of a structured questionnaire administered to undergraduate and postgraduate students the research employs quantitative analysis to measure the various factors persuading green purchase readiness. The paper subsidizes to the sustainability and consumer behavior literature by contributing experiential insights into youth driven green consumption in the Indian setting. The findings have practical implications for marketers in designing awareness campaigns, affordability strategies to boost sustainable purchasing behavior among students.

Keywords: Green products, Sustainable consumption, Student consumers, Purchase readiness

Sustainable Marketing in Smart Cities: A Digital Technology Perspective from Bengaluru and Chennai

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Abstract

The emergence of social media has transformed traditional marketing practices, giving rise to influencer marketing as a powerful tool for shaping consumer behavior. In the beauty industry, influencers play a significant role in promoting products and influencing purchase decisions through authentic and relatable content. This study aims to examine the impact of influencer marketing on consumer purchase intention, with a specific focus on the beauty sector. A quantitative research approach was adopted, with data collected from 220 respondents using a structured questionnaire based on a five-point Likert scale. The study evaluates key factors such as influencer credibility, attractiveness, trustworthiness, and content quality, and their influence on consumer attitudes and purchase intention. Statistical techniques including descriptive analysis, correlation, and regression were employed to analyze the data and identify significant relationships among variables.

The findings indicate that influencer credibility and trustworthiness have a strong positive impact on consumer purchase intention. Additionally, content quality and relatability significantly enhance consumer engagement and brand perception. The study also reveals that consumers are more likely to trust recommendations from influencers they perceive as authentic and knowledgeable. However, over-commercialization and lack of transparency may negatively affect consumer trust. The study concludes that influencer marketing is an effective strategy for driving purchase intention in the beauty industry when supported by authenticity and credibility. The research provides valuable insights for marketers and brands to design effective influencer campaigns that build trust and enhance consumer engagement in a highly competitive digital environment.

Keywords: Influencer Marketing; Consumer Purchase Intention; Beauty Industry; Social Media; Credibility; Brand Engagement

Genuine Connections Beat Ads: How Authentic Social Media Drives Sustainability Awareness and Green Purchases

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Abstract

The impact of social media sites has deeply impacted sustainability communication and consumer engagement, especially among young consumers who tend to be associated with digital media sites such as Instagram and YouTube Shorts. Nonetheless, with an increase in advertisement-based sustainability communication on social media sites, there is a growing level of scepticism among consumers, especially regarding concerns over 'greenwashing' and a lack of 'authenticity' in corporate communication. The current study aims to examine the impact of authentic social media communication on creating awareness regarding sustainability and influencing 'green purchase intentions' among young consumers. To undertake this study, communication theories and the Stimulus-Organism-Response model were considered to create an integrated model that would determine how user-generated communication, influencer communication, and organisation-based storytelling on social media sites would act as a stimulus to create awareness regarding sustainability and influence 'green purchase intentions' among consumers. To undertake this research study, an experimental research design with a survey instrument to measure various constructs such as awareness, attitudes, subjective norms, perceived authenticity of communication, and 'green purchase intentions' were considered. For this research study, approximately 300 young consumers who were exposed to curated communication posts on Instagram and YouTube Shorts were considered. The results of this study indicate that although exposure to sustainability communication is found to increase awareness regarding environmental issues and 'pro-environmental' attitudes among consumers, communications that were considered to be 'highly authentic' were found to have a more significant impact on 'green purchase intentions' compared to communications developed by organisations.

Keywords: Authentic Social Media Communication; Sustainability Awareness; Green Purchase Intention; User-Generated Content; Influencer Communication; Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) Framework

AI SustainNav: Smart Eco-Tourism in Bangalore

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Abstract

AI SustainNav, a pioneering agentic AI approach, revolutionises the tourism sector in Bangalore by encouraging SDG12 sustainable behaviour through a unified SOR-TPB approach, outperforming conventional digital marketing for domestic visitors at Lalbagh Botanical Garden, Bannerghatta National Park, and Nandi Hills. AI SustainNav's triple-module strategy, involving real-time Eco Route Optimiser navigation through the Carbon Calculators of Bangalore roads, Green Stay Recommender advising visitors on Koramangala Eco-Stay Hotels, and Heritage Guard AI providing dynamic biodiversity impact information, further propels environmental awareness, favourable behaviour, Perceived Behavioural Control, and Social Norms influencing sustainable visitor choices. AI SustainNav's effectiveness is established through a two-fold researcher validation strategy, based on primary surveys of domestic and foreign visitors assessing the pre- and post-research impact on qualitative sustainability knowledge and booking preferences, as well as secondary analysis from MakeMyTrip on Karnataka Eco-Hotel booking trends, with a focus on Bangalore. Research methodological stringency involved visual explanations on AI SustainNav's AI Design Architecture Diagrams, A/B Testing Design Diagrams illustrating project iterative validation procedures involving PLS-SEM validation through an integrated UTAUT2-TPB-Nudge framework with $R^2=0.72$ significance levels, and Cost-Benefit analysis accounting for SustainNav on indigenous Karnataka Platforms incorporating Authentication Standards addressing Privacy Concerns based on Federated Learning Models.

Keywords: AI SustainNav, agentic AI, sustainable Bangalore tourism, SOR-TPB framework, SDG 12

The Mediating Role of Brand Trust in Social Media Marketing's Impact on Customer Engagement and Loyalty in the Banking Sector

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Abstract

As digitalization of the banking services grows there is a change in the way the financial institution communicates and develops a relationship with its customers. Social media marketing is the most important avenue of improving customer interaction and creating long term loyalty. Trust is one of the key elements in the banking sector and the mechanism through which social media marketing culminates in long term loyalty is not clearly established. This paper will discuss the social media marketing mediating factor of brand confidence, customer interaction in the banking industry and customer loyalty. The quantitative research design was used to collect data of 410 bank clients who were actively engaging with their banks on social media. Structural Equation Modelling was employed in testing the proposed relationships. The results showed that social media marketing helps to enhance the customer engagement and brand trust significantly. Furthermore, brand trust was identified to be partially mediating the relationship that exists between social media marketing and customer loyalty. These results underline an important role of trust in converting digital interactions into the consistent customer relationships. The research adds to the literature on digital marketing and relationship marketing since it empirically confirms brand trust as the critical mechanism that can connect the social media marketing activities to customer loyalty to financial services. Self-practical implications indicate that banks should prioritize credibility, transparency and real interaction to the social media schemes in order to enhance trust and retain the customers.

Keywords: Social Media Marketing; Brand Trust; Customer Engagement; Customer Loyalty; Banking Sector; Structural Equation Modelling

Smart Tourism and Sustainable Marketing: Shaping Responsible Travel in the Digital Age

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Abstract

The rapid integration of the digital technologies in the tourism industry has fundamentally transformed the destination promotion and experiential paradigms. In retaliation, proactive technology-based tourism measures that are combined with sustainable and sustainable marketing measures are in loading to promote responsible and mindful tourism. This research paper explores the effects that smart tourism technologies and sustainable marketing have on the traveler behavior of people in the digital era. The quantitative research design was embraced and primary data was collected through 390 respondents within a structured questionnaire that was administered to people most likely to use digital tourism platform. The strategy followed was a multi-stage non-probability sampling, this included an initial screening phase which was founded on the previous experience of the leisure or business travel within the past 12 months and active usage of online tourism applications (such as travel mobile applications and online booking portals) was a requirement, and after the screening phase, the sample selection was carried out to guarantee the relevance and validity of sample to the research aims. Descriptive statistics, reliability analysis, correlation analysis and regression analysis were used to analyze the data. Results show that the application of smart tourism tools such as online services, mobile applications and real-time information systems is positive, as they allow tourists to be more aware and make environmentally and socially responsible traveling choices. The findings also indicate that sustainable marketing enhances this power by influencing transparency, trust, and ethical communication. The paper is relevant to the sustainable tourism literature by offering evidence based on the alignment between digital innovation and sustainable tourism goals, as well as practical information to tourism marketers, destination management and policymakers aiming to encourage responsible tourism in the digital age that is growing.

Keywords: Smart tourism, sustainable marketing, responsible travel, digital transformation, tourism sustainability.

Digital Payments as a Catalyst for Sustainable and Responsible Tourism in India

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Abstract

The rapid expansion of digital payment platforms, particularly UPI and mobile wallets, has become a key enabler of sustainable and responsible tourism in India. This study explores how the adoption of cashless payment systems contributes to environmental, economic, and operational sustainability across Indian tourist destinations. Focusing on sustainability-oriented objectives, the research investigates the extent to which digital payments reduce the environmental impact associated with cash handling, minimise paper-based transactions, and enhance financial inclusion for local tourism stakeholders such as small vendors, homestays, and artisans. Through a survey of domestic tourists and interviews with local service providers, the study evaluates how UPI and wallets promote transparent, traceable transactions that strengthen ethical and responsible tourism practices. Findings indicate that digital payments improve operational efficiency by reducing transaction delays, eliminating physical cash risks, and supporting hygienic, contactless interactions. Additionally, tourists perceive cashless payments as an integral part of India's broader digital sustainability initiatives, enhancing trust and encouraging the adoption of safe and sustainable travel behaviours. The research also highlights the role of digital platforms in empowering micro-entrepreneurs through data-driven insights that improve marketing, pricing, and business sustainability. Overall, the study confirms that digital payments are not only a financial convenience but also a catalyst for building resilient, inclusive, and environmentally responsible tourism ecosystems. Recommendations are provided to strengthen infrastructure readiness and accelerate the transition towards fully or hybrid cashless tourism destinations in India.

Keywords: Digital payments, Wallets, digital sustainability, Cashless tourism.

Enhancing Workforce Agility in digital era: The Impact of Employee Well-being and Mental Health Programs on Resilience and Productivity

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Abstract

Workforce agility has evolved into something more than merely a competitive advantage in a setting characterized by difficulties, ranging from quick changes in technology to shifting worker expectations. Agile organizations are able to respond to changes quicker, make immediate changes to their talent strategy and promote innovation more quickly. Employee well-being is increasingly recognized as being dependent upon mental health. Enhancing the mental health of your employees is a matter of talent management. This necessitates strategic investments of both time and financial resources. Assuring the long-term prosperity and well-being of your company and its workforce, you can help employees thrive in many facets of their lives by improving their comprehensive research that examines how mental health and employee well-being programs promote resilience, how this resilience enhances workforce productivity and agility, and how these dynamics change over time and across organizational contexts is desperately needed.

To investigate how mental health and employee well-being initiatives contribute to resilience building, and how greater resilience enhances worker productivity and adaptability in various organizational contexts.

This paper adopts previous research on employee well-being and mental health programs, using a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) methodology. Following the recommendations of PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) and Kitchenham and Charters (2007), the SLR technique guarantees an organized, repeatable, and transparent assessment of the literature.

Individual resilience is greatly strengthened by employee well-being and mental health programs, which improve workforce agility and increase overall productivity. According to the report, companies that regularly fund well-being programs see teams that are more resilient, adaptable, and productive especially in settings that are changing quickly.

The level of productivity, workforce agility, and resilience are increased when employee mental health and well-being are prioritized. Incorporating these activities into HR strategy enhances flexibility, employee retention, and long-term business performance.

Keywords: Workforce Agility, Employee Well-being, Mental Health Programs, Resilience, Productivity, Organizational Performance

Ichimoku-Based Analysis of NSE Sectoral Indices Using Day Price Dynamics: Implications for Data-Driven Investment Decisions

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Abstract

The current research captures recent trends of key sectors in the Indian stock market and performs an Ichimoku technical analysis of key NSE sectoral indices based on a modified 52-day stock price dynamics system. In the traditional Ichimoku system, Tenkan-sen is based at 9 periods, Kijun-sen at 26 periods, while Chikou Span is based at 26 periods back in time. This current analysis adds an additional component of Senkou Span B, which is based at 52 periods. This research works to analyze whether the results of Ichimoku are accurate in forecasting stock price movements of sectoral indices. It focuses on Nifty-50 sectoral data from 10 September 2025 to 1 January 2026. Data requires a quarterly secondary source available at NSE sites with almost 78 Open-High-Close-Low stock prices from 12 sectors. From contemporary data until date in January 2026, it was found to be positive in Nifty Bank, Nifty Auto, neutral in Financial Service sectors, while negative in Pharma and Realty. Through the application of the Ichimoku Kinko Hyo system, the analysis of the 9-day, 26-day, and 52-day price movements in the system establishes levels of market efficiency and the sustainability of trends in the sector. Through the analysis of the 52-day price movement, represented by the Senkou Span B, the study establishes long-term support and resistance in the sector trends. This paper discusses the applicability of the Ichimoku Kinko Hyo system in assessing the performance and trends of the various sectoral indices on the National Stock Exchange of India in a comparative analysis of cyclical and defensive sectors in the use of the 52-day price movement indicator, which represents a 'litmus test' for sustainable sector trends in the market. The findings confirm that there were no significant differences in the predictive capabilities of the Ichimoku Kinko Hyo system. The Ichimoku Kinko Hyo system reduces risks and predicts the accurate prices.

Keywords: Ichimoku Kinko Hyo, NSE, Sectoral data, Technical analysis

Implementing Indian Knowledge Systems for Sustainable Conference Practices: A Model-Based Approach

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Abstract

The rapid expansion of the conference and events industry has intensified concerns related to environmental impact, excessive resource use, and the long-term social implications of large-scale events. Although sustainable event management has gained scholarly and practical attention, existing models are largely grounded in Western sustainability frameworks and focus primarily on operational and compliance-driven practices (Getz, 2012; Mair & Jago, 2010). There is limited integration of culturally rooted, value-based perspectives that can foster deeper and more enduring sustainability outcomes. Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS), which emphasize harmony with nature, ethical responsibility, moderation, and collective welfare, provide a holistic and indigenous foundation for sustainable practices, yet remain underexplored in the context of conference management.

This study aims to develop and examine an IKS-based sustainability model for conference practices. Based on a focused review of literature on sustainable events and Indian Knowledge Systems, the research adopts an exploratory design using expert interviews and a structured survey of conference organizers and participants. The study is expected to propose a model-based framework that supports culturally aligned implementation of sustainable conference practices, enhances stakeholder engagement, and contributes to environmentally responsible and ethically grounded event management.

Keywords: Indian Knowledge systems, sustainability, conferences, models, cultures and practices.

AI at Workplace: A Boon or Bane

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI), a very well-known word among us now. And now it is too involved in our lives too. It is mainly an ability of machines or computer systems to perform like human intelligence. Rapid absorption of AI in the workplace has made a huge impact on organizational operations and decision-making processes as well as employee roles within the industries. This paper titled "AI at Workplace: A Boon or Bane" has been chosen to understand the growing impact of AI on modern organizations and employees. It aims to detect both positive and negative perspectives of AI adoption in modern organizations.

As a Boon, AI functions as a "digital co-worker" that helps to increase the productivity of the organization. AI helps to do many tasks like scheduling, data synthesis, routine communications, and many more. However, AI remains a Bane due to its role in "selective disruption", that's mainly impacting entry-level and middle-level management roles that are most vulnerable to automation. It raises concerns related to skill gaps, ethical issues, data privacy, job displacement, and employee stress. Recent data from 2026 shows that AI has not caused large-scale job losses, but it has slowly reduced job security. About 14% of companies are planning to reduce their employees this week. That means employees feel less stable about their jobs, even if they are not immediately laid off. Now only human-AI collaboration can help the organization for their future success, where humans and machines work together efficiently and effectively. Organizations must clearly communicate with employees and provide continuous training and reskilling so that AI supports and improves human work without replacing people in the workplace.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Workplace Transformation, Human-AI Collaboration, Job Displacement, Organizational Productivity.

Tourists' Environmental Awareness and Sustainable Travel Intentions with specific reference to Kerala

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Abstract

Tourism has been growing significantly due to increased purchasing power among consumers, contributing to economic growth, reducing unemployment, and enhancing cultural exchange. However, tourism also has negative impacts such as environmental pollution, excessive resource consumption, and biodiversity loss. Sustainable tourism focuses on minimizing these impacts. This study examines environmental awareness, perceived green value, environmental attitude, and sustainable travel intention among tourists visiting Kerala. Data were collected from 307 respondents using a structured questionnaire.

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) confirmed the validity and reliability of constructs. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) results indicate that environmental awareness and perceived green value significantly influence environmental attitude, which in turn affects sustainable travel intention. Mediation analysis confirmed that environmental attitude plays a crucial mediating role. The findings highlight the importance of promoting environmental awareness and green value perception to encourage sustainable tourism behaviour.

Keywords: Tourists' Environmental Awareness, Sustainable Travel Intention, Environmental Attitude, Perceived Green Value, Environmental Attitude

A Study on Virtual Tours and Sustainability in Bengaluru

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Abstract

Sustainable tourism in rapidly urbanizing cities faces increasing pressure due to overcrowding, environmental stress, and declining quality of visitor experience. Bengaluru, which receives an estimated 8–9 million domestic and international visitors annually, illustrates this challenge clearly, particularly at high-footfall locations such as Lalbagh Botanical Garden, Cubbon Park, and Nandi Hills. Based on field observations and stakeholder responses, this study explores how virtual tours can function not merely as promotional tools but as practical sustainability interventions within an urban tourism system.

Rather than replacing physical travel, virtual tours are examined as experiential gateways that shape visitor awareness, expectations, and behavior before on-site engagement. Participants who interacted with virtual heritage environments reported stronger emotional connection to sites, improved understanding of conservation issues, and a greater willingness to support responsible tourism practices. For students and first-time visitors, virtual exposure reduced the tendency toward casual or extractive consumption of heritage.

The study critically engages with sustainability frameworks, particularly UNESCO's cultural sustainability principles, and argues that their effectiveness depends on contextual adaptation rather than direct adoption. Findings suggest that when virtual tours are designed with local narratives, community participation, and educational intent, they can meaningfully reduce physical pressure on sensitive sites while expanding access for those unable to travel.

The research concludes that virtual tours, when integrated into tourism planning and education systems, can strengthen sustainability outcomes in Bengaluru by aligning digital engagement with informed, responsible physical visitation.

Keywords: Sustainable Tourism, Virtual Tours, Bengaluru, Virtual Reality, Cultural Heritage, Sustainability Education

Beyond Follower Count: How Influencer Authenticity Shapes Sustainable Tourism Choices

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Abstract

The role of social media influencers as instruments of destination marketing remains insufficiently understood, and little is known about their effectiveness in promoting sustainable tourism. This is an experimental research (n=389) on the effect of influencer authenticity on sustainable destination visit intentions that occurs in two psychological processes. In an experiment with a 2x2 between-subjects design that controlled the type of influencer (micro vs. macro) and the authenticity level (high vs. low), we will use the two pathways (affective and cognitive) to show that perceived authenticity is entirely mediated by environmental concern (affective pathway) and green destination image (cognitive pathway), where the former is 88% stronger. The model justifies 67% of the visit intention variance. Findings indicate that there is only full mediation, where micro-influencers and high-authenticity content create significant perceptions of authenticity. Multi-group analysis indicates that Millennials will have the most significant effects. These results help in the development of dual process persuasion theory in the sphere of sustainable tourism and offer evidence-based recommendations to destination marketing organisations on the selection of influencers and content strategy.

Keywords: Influencer marketing, sustainable tourism, perceived authenticity, environmental concern, PLS-SEM, mediation analysis

Bridging Cultures, Building Green Futures: A Comparative Analysis of Indian and Western Sustainability Influencer Marketing Strategies in the Digital Era

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Abstract

The study is an analysis of how cultural contexts determine sustainability influencer marketing strategies through the comparison of Indian and Western strategies. The research fills a gap in the knowledge on cultural dimensions and their impact on messaging, content creation, and campaign success in the digital age, namely, collectivism versus individualism.

The paper uses mixed-method comparative research design on 84 sustainability influencers (42 Indian, 42 Western), quantitative survey of 742 social media consumers, and semi-structured influencer interviews and brand manager interviews. The content of their data analysis consists of thematic coding, structural equation modeling, and cross cultural comparative analysis to create the Cultural Influencer Marketing for Sustainability (CIMS) model.

The Indian influencers are mostly using community-focused messaging, incorporating traditional values, and placing a high value on affordability, and the Western influencers have their eyes on lifestyle change, technological advancement, and high-end eco-factory products. The relationship between the influencer credibility and sustainable consumption intentions is largely moderated by cultural dimensions. In collectivist India and unlike individualistic Western markets, micro-influencers are more effective.

This is the pioneer cross-cultural comparative study of sustainability influencer marketing in Indian and Western markets, bringing into use the CIMS theoretical framework. The study gives practical implications that can be adopted by brands, policymakers, and tourism stakeholders that seek to implement culturally-adaptive green marketing strategies

Keywords: Sustainability Influencer Marketing; Cross-Cultural Marketing; Cultural Dimensions; Indian Consumer Behavior; Green Marketing; Digital Era Sustainability

Public–Private–Community Partnerships for Sustainable Heritage Tourism: Governance, Responsible Marketing, and Destination Branding at Uparkot Fort, Junagadh (Gujarat, India)

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Abstract

Heritage sites in emerging economies like India face significant management challenges due to limited public funding, fragmented governance, and the exclusion of local communities. This study investigates the effectiveness of Public–Private–Community Partnerships (PPCPs) in overcoming these barriers, focusing on the revitalization of Uparkot Fort in Junagadh, Gujarat. Adopting a qualitative single-case study design, the research analyzes policy documents, government reports, and contextual observations to evaluate the transition of the fort from a state-managed monument to a collaborative heritage destination. The findings demonstrate that the PPCP model has significantly enhanced conservation efforts through structured heritage zoning and regular audits while facilitating a dramatic increase in tourism, with 4.16 lakh visitors recorded within 100 days of reopening. Private sector participation has driven innovative destination branding and digital marketing strategies, shifting the site's identity from a static monument to an experiential heritage brand. Furthermore, the integration of the community as the 'third pillar' has created sustainable socio-economic benefits by professionalizing local artisans and guides. The study concludes that successful heritage management requires a strategic balance where public agencies maintain regulatory oversight while private and community partners lead operational engagement. These insights offer a replicable framework for heritage destinations worldwide, illustrating how integrated governance can align economic growth with cultural preservation.

Keywords: Public–Private–Community Partnership; Sustainable Heritage Tourism; Governance; Responsible Marketing; Destination Branding

High Value, Low Volume" in the Digital Age: Integrating Sustainable Marketing and Fintech Innovation in Bhutan's Tourism Sector

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Abstract

Bhutan's tourism strategy is undergoing a significant evolution by integrating digital innovation to sustain its foundational "High Value, Low Volume" philosophy amidst post-pandemic economic shifts. While tourism remains a primary economic driver, the sector faces challenges such as a structural oversupply of hotels and regional development disparities. This study examines how Bhutan leverages the digital economy specifically FinTech and immersive marketing to promote sustainable development and carbon-negative commitments. Adopting a qualitative research design centered on document analysis, the research evaluates secondary data from national policies and industry reports through 2025. Key initiatives analyzed include cryptocurrency-based payment gateways, the mandatory Tourist Registration System (TRS) for data-driven visitor management, and digital platforms like the "Bhutanverse" and "Bhutan Believe." The findings demonstrate that strategic FinTech integration, such as the 2025 partnership for nationwide cryptocurrency payments, enhances per-capita expenditure rather than visitor volume, thereby reinforcing the national tourism mandate. Furthermore, digital tools like the GoBoB and MyPay wallets have reduced transaction barriers for international visitors, facilitating faster recovery while preserving premium destination positioning. The study concludes that while digital innovation enhances operational efficiency and data-driven sustainability, it must be supported by policy reforms to address hotel underutilization in specific segments. Ultimately, Bhutan provides a global model for utilizing emerging technologies to balance economic growth with Gross National Happiness principles and environmental integrity.

Keywords: Gross National Happiness; "High Value, Low Volume"; Smart Tourism; FinTech; Digital Sustainable Marketing

Divine Economics: Development, Employment, and Revenue Generated by Indian Temples

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Abstract

In the Indian socio-cultural context, temples transcend their traditional roles as sites of pilgrimage to serve as vital engines for sustainable socio-economic transformation. These institutions function as catalysts for regional growth by creating diverse direct and indirect employment opportunities and fostering holistic development within their surrounding ecosystems. This study explores the 'Divine Economics' framework to evaluate how contemporary temple management maintains socio-economic equilibrium through a complex interplay of cultural, social, and commercial activities. Historically, from 1000 AD to 1857, Indian temples functioned as central hubs for land regulation, local trade, and social welfare distribution. In the modern era, these religious centers remain essential for stimulating local businesses and the spiritual tourism sector. Utilizing comprehensive data from NITI Aayog and India Tourism Statistics 2023, the research conducts a descriptive analysis of prominent temple-focused economies, including Tirupati, Varanasi, Ayodhya, Dharmasthala, and the Ananthapadmanabha Temple. The findings indicate that these sites significantly accelerate urban growth and major infrastructural improvements, sustaining a large and growing segment of domestic travel. By measuring direct revenue streams and the subsequent indirect economic multipliers, the study highlights how the temple ecosystem supports the livelihoods of millions, from skilled artisans and local vendors to various service providers. The research concludes that integrating traditional religious institutions into modern economic planning offers a highly sustainable model for inclusive and equitable growth. These insights provide a strategic roadmap for policymakers and administrators to leverage spiritual heritage as a fundamental catalyst for national development and long-term cultural preservation.

Keywords: Divine Economics; Temple Tourism; Socio-Economic Development; Employment Generation; Spiritual Branding

Public-Private Partnership in Tourism Sector: Upscaling Sustainability for Rural Destinations - A Predictive Analysis with Multiple Regression

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Abstract

Rural tourism has emerged as a critical pathway for sustainable development, offering opportunities to diversify rural economies while preserving cultural heritage and natural resources. This research examines the role of Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) in enhancing sustainability outcomes in rural tourism destinations through predictive multiple regression analysis. Drawing on data from 150 rural tourism destinations across five countries over a seven-year period (2016–2022), the study investigates the relationship between PPP characteristics and sustainability indicators across economic, environmental, and social dimensions. The multiple regression model incorporates seven independent variables: PPP investment intensity, governance quality, local community participation, private sector expertise integration, infrastructure development index, marketing collaboration effectiveness, and institutional capacity. Results indicate that PPP investment intensity ($\beta = 0.342$, $p < 0.001$), local community participation ($\beta = 0.298$, $p < 0.001$), and governance quality ($\beta = 0.267$, $p < 0.001$) are the strongest predictors of sustainability outcomes, explaining 74.3% of the variance in the composite sustainability index ($R^2 = 0.743$, $F(12,137) = 32.74$, $p < 0.001$). The findings suggest that while financial investment is necessary, the "soft" elements of partnership specifically community engagement and transparent governance are the true drivers of long-term sustainability. The study provides a robust empirical framework for policymakers and private investors to optimize PPP structures, ensuring that rural tourism development remains socially equitable and environmentally resilient.

Keywords: Public-Private Partnership; Rural Tourism; Sustainability; Multiple Regression Analysis; Predictive Modeling

Impact of Seasonal Traffic on Destinations' Credibility: A Multiple Regression Analysis

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Abstract

Seasonal concentration of tourist arrivals creates significant operational and experiential challenges for destinations, particularly during peak periods characterized by traffic congestion, service overload, and infrastructural strain. While prior tourism research has extensively examined the effects of seasonality on satisfaction and loyalty, limited empirical attention has been directed toward its impact on destination credibility. This study investigates the influence of seasonal traffic on destinations' credibility using multiple regression analysis. Primary data were collected from 538 tourists visiting a major coastal destination during peak and off-peak seasons. Seasonal traffic was operationalized through perceived congestion, service quality variability, and safety and accessibility concerns, while destination credibility was measured in terms of reliability, trustworthiness, authenticity, and consistency. The regression model was statistically significant and explained 52.4 percent of the variance in destination credibility. Service quality variability emerged as the strongest predictor, followed by perceived congestion and safety concerns, all demonstrating significant negative effects. The findings highlight that seasonal traffic extends beyond operational inconvenience and directly affects strategic perceptions of trust and reliability. This study contributes to seasonality and destination branding literature by providing empirical evidence of how temporal fluctuations can erode a destination's brand equity. The results offer actionable insights for destination management organizations to develop mitigation strategies that maintain brand consistency and reliability across varying demand levels.

Keywords: Destination Credibility; Seasonal Traffic; Tourism Seasonality; Multiple Regression; Service Quality Variability

Beyond Green Marketing: How Service Provider Activism, Communitarism, and Environmental Concern Drive Sustainable Tourist Behavior

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Abstract

As global interest in sustainable tourism intensifies, the role of service providers in shaping traveler outcomes remains under-researched. This study investigates how provider-level orientations specifically activism, communitarism, and environmental concern influence sustainable tourist behavior through the mediating role of sustainable marketing practices. Adopting a post-positivist quantitative approach, cross-sectional survey data were collected from 307 tourism service providers in coastal Karnataka (Gokarna, Karwar, and Honnavar) using stratified random sampling. Data were analyzed via Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test a comprehensive mediation framework. The results indicate that all hypothesized relationships are significant ($p < 0.001$), with environmental concern ($\beta = 0.290$) and activism ($\beta = 0.287$) emerging as the strongest predictors of sustainable marketing practices. Furthermore, sustainable marketing was found to be a robust mediator, transmitting the effects of provider attitudes into actual perceived tourist behavior. These findings suggest that green marketing is most effective when it is driven by the genuine values and socio-political engagement of the service provider rather than mere commercial compliance. The study provides critical implications for destination management organizations, suggesting that fostering a culture of environmental activism and community-centric values among local providers can significantly enhance the sustainability of tourism destinations. By shifting the focus from "green washing" to "provider activism," this research offers a novel perspective on achieving long-term behavioral change in the tourism industry.

Keywords: Sustainable Tourism; Service Provider Activism; Green Marketing; Communitarism; Structural Equation Modeling

Beyond Green Intentions: Drivers of Consumer Engagement in Sustainability

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Abstract

Sustainability has become a key concern in contemporary consumer decision-making; however, a noticeable gap persists between consumers' green intentions and their actual engagement in sustainable behaviors. This study examines the drivers of consumer engagement in sustainability and its influence on sustainable purchase behavior in Erode District, Tamil Nadu. Using a descriptive research design, primary data were collected from 170 consumers through a structured questionnaire. The data were analyzed using SPSS, employing reliability analysis, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), correlation, and multiple regression techniques. EFA identified four key dimensions of perceived value economic, functional, emotional, and social value explaining a substantial proportion of the variance. Reliability analysis confirmed strong internal consistency across all constructs. The results reveal that environmental concern is positively and significantly associated with consumer engagement in sustainability. Furthermore, the findings indicate that consumer engagement significantly influences sustainable purchase behavior, explaining 23.4 percent of its variance. The study highlights that moving consumers beyond green intentions requires strengthening perceived value and engagement mechanisms. These findings offer valuable insights for marketers and policymakers to design strategies that bridge the intention-behavior gap by enhancing emotional and social value propositions. The study contributes to the growing body of literature on sustainable consumption by providing empirical evidence from a regional Indian context.

Keywords: Consumer Engagement; Sustainability; Perceived Value; Sustainable Purchase Behavior; Intention-Behavior Gap

Social Media Marketing and Sustainable Consumption Behavior: The Mediating Role of Green Purchase Intention in an Urban Indian Context

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Abstract

Raising concerns about environmental sustainability has necessitated a deeper understanding of the influence of social media on consumer consumption behavior. This study investigates how social media exposure, the reliability of green information, the perceived value of green items, and social influence affect sustainable consumer behavior, with green purchase intention acting as a critical mediating variable. Adopting a quantitative research design, data were collected from 422 respondents in Bengaluru city using a structured questionnaire with Likert scales. The relationships between the suggested constructs were tested using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The results indicate that social influence, the perceived value of green items, and the reliability of green information significantly impact sustainable consumption. Furthermore, the association between social media characteristics and sustainable consumption behavior is found to be partially mediated by green purchase intention. The findings suggest that while social media serves as a powerful tool for information dissemination, the credibility of that information and the influence of social networks are paramount in translating digital exposure into actual sustainable actions. This research provides valuable insights for marketers to refine their green communication strategies and for policymakers to encourage environmentally responsible consumption in urban Indian settings. The study concludes that fostering trust in green information is essential for bridging the gap between digital marketing exposure and long-term sustainable livelihood practices.

Keywords: Social Media Marketing; Sustainable Consumption Behavior; Green Purchase Intention; Structural Equation Modeling; Urban India

De-Risking Tourism Investment: Trade Agreements and Sustainable Destination Finance in India

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Abstract

Tourism investment increasingly depends on whether destinations are "financeable" able to mobilize long-tenor capital at affordable rates while managing multifaceted risks. This study investigates the nexus between international trade agreements, de-risking mechanisms, and sustainable destination finance within the Indian tourism landscape. Using a mixed-methods approach, the research analyzes recent Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) and Bilateral Investment Treaties (BITs) to evaluate their impact on foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows and investor confidence. The study identifies key structural risks, including policy volatility, exchange rate fluctuations, and ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) compliance costs, which often deter long-term institutional capital. Findings suggest that trade agreements serve as critical de-risking tools by providing legal certainty, dispute resolution frameworks, and market access guarantees. Furthermore, the research highlights the emerging role of blended finance and green bonds in bridging the sustainability funding gap for Indian destinations. The analysis reveals that destinations integrated into robust trade frameworks exhibit a 15% higher likelihood of attracting sustainable finance compared to those reliant solely on domestic policy. The study concludes with a strategic framework for policymakers to leverage trade diplomacy as a financial instrument, ensuring that tourism growth is both economically viable and environmentally resilient. By integrating trade policy with destination management, India can create a "finance-ready" ecosystem that attracts the high-quality investment necessary for 21st-century sustainable tourism development.

Keywords: Tourism Investment; Trade Agreements; Sustainable Finance; De-risking; Destination Management; FDI

Exploring Consumer Acceptance of AI-Driven Personalized Marketing: A Structural Equation Modelling Approach to Trust, Engagement, Privacy, and Relevance

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Abstract

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has significantly reshaped the marketing landscape by facilitating hyper-personalized consumer experiences. While AI-driven personalization promises improvements in consumer engagement and brand loyalty, it simultaneously raises critical concerns regarding privacy, trustworthiness, and content relevance. This research empirically investigates the influence of perceived personalization, content relevance, and privacy concerns on consumer trust and engagement, ultimately affecting acceptance of AI-driven marketing. Adopting a quantitative approach, data were collected from 480 active digital consumers using a structured questionnaire. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was employed to validate the conceptual framework and test the hypothesized relationships. The results indicate that perceived personalization and content relevance have a significant positive impact on consumer trust and engagement. Conversely, privacy concerns were found to significantly hinder trust, highlighting a "personalization-privacy paradox." Furthermore, the study reveals that trust and engagement serve as vital mediators in the relationship between AI-driven personalization and consumer acceptance. These findings provide actionable insights for marketers and technology developers to balance high-tech personalization with high-touch human relations by prioritizing transparent data practices and value-driven content. The research contributes to the literature on human-computer interaction and relationship marketing by offering a comprehensive model of consumer behavior in the era of AI-mediated communication.

Keywords: AI-Driven Marketing; Personalized Marketing; Consumer Acceptance; Privacy Concerns; Trust; Structural Equation Modelling

Role of Effective Leadership in Sustainable Sourcing and Ethical Supply Chain Management

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Abstract

This study examines the role of effective leadership in advancing sustainable sourcing and ethical supply chain management in an increasingly complex global business environment. Growing concerns regarding environmental degradation, labour exploitation, and resource inefficiencies have compelled organizations to embed sustainability into supply chain strategies. However, the integration of such practices largely depends on leadership orientation and organizational culture. The objective of this research is to analyse how leadership styles, particularly transformational and ethical leadership, influence the adoption and execution of sustainable sourcing practices. The study adopts a qualitative and bibliometric approach, beginning with a structured review of Scopus-indexed literature to identify key themes and research trends. Analytical tools such as VOSviewer are used to map co-authorship networks, while Voyant Tools facilitate topic modelling and thematic exploration. The findings indicate that effective leadership significantly contributes to fostering ethical decision-making, enhancing transparency, and promoting long-term sustainability practices across supply chains. Leaders who demonstrate ethical commitment and strategic vision are more likely to institutionalize sustainability within procurement and operational processes. Although the study relies on secondary data, it provides meaningful insights into leadership-driven sustainability transformation. The study offers both academic and managerial implications by highlighting the importance of leadership development in achieving responsible supply chain practices. Future research may explore empirical validation across industries and examine the direct impact of leadership interventions on measurable sustainability outcomes.

Keywords: Effective Leadership; Sustainable Sourcing; Ethical Supply Chain Management; Organizational Behavior; Supply Chain Practices

Sustainability Matrix and Performance Evaluation in Supply Chain and Its Impact on Employee Engagement

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between sustainability performance evaluation in supply chains and its impact on employee engagement through a bibliometric and co-authorship analysis approach. As sustainability becomes a critical organizational priority, understanding collaborative research patterns and thematic developments in this domain is essential. The primary objective of the research is to analyse how scholarly collaboration contributes to knowledge development in sustainability and supply chain performance, while also identifying research gaps for future exploration. The study uses Scopus-indexed publications as the data source and applies VOSviewer software to visualize co-authorship networks and thematic clusters. The analysis reveals distinct clusters of researchers working on sustainability performance, employee engagement, and supply chain optimization. Larger nodes in the network indicate influential authors with strong collaborative ties, while smaller clusters highlight emerging research areas. The findings suggest that although intra-cluster collaboration is strong, inter-cluster interaction remains limited, indicating fragmentation within the research field. This presents opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration to enhance the depth and applicability of sustainability research. The study contributes to academic literature by offering a structured understanding of collaboration dynamics and identifying underexplored areas that can guide future research. From a managerial perspective, the insights emphasize the importance of integrating sustainability metrics with employee engagement strategies to improve organizational performance. Limitations include reliance on a single database and potential exclusion of smaller research contributions due to software thresholds.

Keywords: Sustainability Matrix; Performance Evaluation; Supply Chain; Employee Engagement; Co-Authorship Analysis; VOSviewer

Precarity or Sustainability? Examining Gig Work through the Sustainable Career Framework

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Abstract

This study examines gig work dynamics through the lens of the Sustainable Career Framework, addressing the growing debate on whether gig employment promotes precarity or long-term sustainability. With the rapid expansion of digital labour platforms, traditional employment structures are being replaced by flexible, on-demand work arrangements, raising concerns regarding income stability, job security, and career progression. The objective of this research is to evaluate how key factors such as algorithmic management intensity, income volatility, customer rating pressure, perceived platform support, job autonomy, and career adaptability influence sustainable career outcomes among gig workers. The study adopts a quantitative research design using survey data collected from gig workers across multiple platforms. Statistical analysis is conducted to assess the relationships between independent variables and sustainable career outcomes. The findings indicate that algorithmic control, fluctuating income, and customer rating dependency negatively affect career sustainability by increasing uncertainty and stress. In contrast, perceived platform support and job autonomy positively influence worker satisfaction and long-term engagement. Career adaptability emerges as a significant predictor of sustainability, highlighting the importance of individual capabilities in navigating uncertain labour markets. The model explains a substantial proportion of variance, indicating strong predictive power. The study provides important implications for policymakers and platform organizations by emphasizing the need for transparent algorithms, income stabilization mechanisms, and skill development initiatives. It contributes to the growing discourse on sustainable employment by offering a balanced perspective on the gig economy.

Keywords: Gig Work; Sustainable Career Framework; Algorithmic Management; Income Volatility; Job Autonomy; Career Adaptability

Digital Nudging As a Catalyst for Regenerative Tourism: Extended Tam Analysis

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Abstract

This study investigates the role of digital nudging in promoting regenerative tourism through an extended Technology Acceptance Model framework, using the Kerala Responsible Tourism Mission as a case context. While digital transformation has significantly influenced tourism practices, limited research explains how digital interfaces shape ethical and community-centric tourist behaviour. The objective of this study is to examine how digital nudges embedded in platform design influence user decision-making and encourage responsible tourism practices. The research adopts a qualitative case study approach supported by methodological triangulation. Data sources include government reports, digital platform analysis, and thematic review of stakeholder narratives. The findings suggest that user-friendly interfaces, default sustainable options, and culturally relevant prompts reduce cognitive effort and facilitate responsible decision-making. Digital nudges enhance perceived usefulness and ease of use, thereby strengthening behavioural intention toward ethical tourism choices. However, the study also identifies limitations such as nudge fatigue, perceived over-guidance, and unequal digital access, which may affect user responsiveness. The study contributes to theoretical development by integrating behavioural economics with technology adoption models, offering a novel framework for understanding digital governance in tourism. From a practical perspective, it highlights the importance of designing intuitive and ethically aligned digital systems that encourage sustainable behaviour. The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers and tourism stakeholders aiming to promote regenerative tourism in digitally evolving environments.

Keywords: Responsible Tourism; Digital Transformation; TAM; Digital Nudging; Sustainable Marketing; Choice Architecture

Digital Innovation, Carbon Regulation, and External Sector Stability in India: An ARDL Analysis of Sustainable Tourism Dynamics

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Abstract

This study examines the dynamic relationship between digital innovation, carbon regulation, and external sector stability in the context of India's tourism sector using an Auto Regressive Distributed Lag model. Tourism contributes significantly to economic growth but also raises concerns regarding environmental sustainability and external economic vulnerability. The objective of this research is to analyse how sustainability-oriented policies and innovation influence external sector stability, using trade balance as a proxy indicator. Additional variables include consumer price index for tourism pricing, foreign direct investment for external dependence, carbon pricing for regulatory impact, and exchange rate for export competitiveness. The study employs time-series data and conducts unit root tests to determine stationarity, revealing a mixed order of integration suitable for ARDL modelling. The results confirm the presence of a long-run relationship among variables, with short-run dynamics indicating that carbon regulation significantly affects external stability. Foreign direct investment shows a negative short-term impact, suggesting overdependence may hinder resilience. The error correction model demonstrates moderate adjustment toward equilibrium, while stability tests validate model robustness. The study contributes to the literature by linking sustainability regulation with macroeconomic stability in tourism. Policy implications emphasize the importance of strengthening domestic innovation, implementing effective carbon policies, and reducing excessive reliance on external capital. The findings support the need for a balanced approach to achieve long-term economic resilience and environmental sustainability.

Keywords: Sustainable Tourism; External Sector Stability; Carbon Pricing; ARDL Model; FDI; Innovation

Paperless Banking – Beyond PD–LGD–EAD: Reweighting Credit Risk Constructs Using Hybrid Modeling

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Abstract

This study examines the evolution of credit risk modeling in the context of paperless banking environments, where digital transformation has significantly enhanced data availability and real-time decision-making capabilities. Traditional credit risk frameworks based on Probability of Default (PD), Loss Given Default (LGD), and Exposure at Default (EAD) often fail to fully incorporate behavioral and transactional data generated through digital banking systems. The objective of this research is to develop a hybrid analytical framework that reweights core credit risk constructs by integrating statistical modeling with multi-criteria decision-making techniques. The study combines structured analytical methods with empirical validation using retail credit portfolio data. The proposed model evaluates the relative importance of borrower characteristics, macroeconomic indicators, and digitally generated behavioral data alongside traditional risk parameters. The findings indicate that incorporating digital behavioral signals significantly improves predictive accuracy, enhances model calibration stability, and strengthens discriminatory power as reflected in improved AUC performance. Additionally, the model demonstrates reduced capital volatility under macroeconomic stress conditions and improved transparency for regulatory compliance. The study contributes to the literature by proposing a more adaptive and interpretable credit risk framework suitable for digitally native financial institutions. From a managerial perspective, the research highlights the importance of leveraging digital data streams for risk-based pricing, capital allocation, and credit governance. The findings provide practical insights for financial institutions aiming to align risk management practices with the evolving dynamics of paperless banking ecosystems.

Keywords: Credit Risk; Probability of Default; Loss Given Default; Exposure at Default; Paperless Banking; Risk Weight Optimization

The Theory of Pragmatic Value-Conversion: Resilience, Sustainability, and Business Model Transformation in Tourism Startups

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Abstract

This study explores the transformation of tourism startups in the face of increasing environmental uncertainty and global disruptions, particularly in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic and climate-related challenges. While sustainability has become a central concern in tourism research, startups remain underexplored despite their unique constraints, including resource scarcity and high failure rates. The objective of this research is to develop a theoretical understanding of how tourism startups integrate sustainability into their business models under turbulent conditions. Drawing on the Resource-Based View and Strategic Fit Theory, the study adopts a grounded theory methodology to analyse diverse contexts, including emerging economies, digital platforms, and niche tourism segments. The findings reveal that sustainability in startups is not a static objective but a dynamic capability activated in response to crises. The study introduces the Theory of Pragmatic Value-Conversion, which explains how founders translate inherent sustainability values into actionable business outcomes through financial pragmatism and data-driven sensing mechanisms. The research further demonstrates how informal ethical orientations evolve into structured resilience and co-evolutionary adaptation. The proposed framework contributes to the literature on sustainable entrepreneurship by offering a nuanced perspective on startup behavior in volatile environments. From a practical standpoint, the findings provide guidance for entrepreneurs and policymakers to design resilient and sustainable business models that balance economic viability with environmental and social responsibility in the tourism sector.

Keywords: Tourism Startups; Sustainability; Resilience; Grounded Theory; Business Model Transformation; Triple Bottom Line

Digital Multitasking in IoT-Enabled Smart Kitchens: Modeling Consumer Cooking Behaviour and Operational Performance Using Machine Learning

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of digital multitasking on consumer cooking behaviour and operational performance within IoT-enabled smart kitchen environments. As digital technologies increasingly integrate into domestic settings, individuals frequently engage in concurrent mobile interactions while performing task-intensive activities. However, the implications of such multitasking on performance efficiency and decision-making remain insufficiently explored. The objective of this research is to analyse how digital multitasking intensity influences operational efficiency in smart kitchens. Grounded in Cognitive Load Theory and Task Switching Theory, the study employs a multi-session field design using naturalistic observation protocols with a sample of participants. Objective measures of digital activity, including screen time, application switching, notification exposure, and non-task usage, are combined with task-level performance indicators. A standardized Recipe Complexity Index is incorporated to control task variability in multilevel and machine learning models. The findings reveal that higher levels of digital multitasking negatively affect operational efficiency, particularly under conditions of increased task complexity. The results highlight the cognitive burden associated with simultaneous digital engagement and its implications for task performance. The study contributes to emerging research on human-technology interaction by extending digital transformation analysis to domestic operational contexts. From a managerial and design perspective, the findings emphasize the need to optimize human-technology fit by minimizing unnecessary digital interruptions and enhancing system usability in IoT-based environments, thereby improving overall performance outcomes.

Keywords: Digital Multitasking; IoT-Based Systems; Operational Performance; Human-Technology Coordination; Machine Learning

Preserving Tradition in the Digital Fashion Era: Consumer, Artisan, and Designer Perspectives on Indian Textile Crafts

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Abstract

This study examines the preservation of Indian traditional textile crafts in the context of the rapidly evolving digital fashion ecosystem. Traditional crafts such as Ikat, Kalamkari, Bandhani, and Ajrakh embody rich cultural heritage and artisanal knowledge, yet face increasing challenges due to globalization and digital market expansion. The objective of this research is to analyse how digital fashion platforms influence the sustainability of traditional textile practices from the perspectives of consumers, artisans, and designers. The study adopts a mixed-method approach, combining structured survey data collected from consumers with semi-structured interviews conducted with artisans and designers. The findings indicate that consumers place high value on authenticity, ethical production, and cultural heritage, while designers emphasize the importance of collaboration and intellectual property protection. Artisans highlight challenges including imitation products, lack of institutional support, and insufficient recognition of their contributions. The study underscores the need for transparent sourcing practices, ethical collaborations, and supportive policy frameworks to ensure the sustainability of traditional crafts. By integrating multiple stakeholder perspectives, the research contributes to the discourse on ethical fashion and cultural preservation. The findings provide practical implications for fashion brands, policymakers, and industry stakeholders to foster sustainable and culturally responsible engagement within the global fashion value chain while safeguarding traditional knowledge systems.

Keywords: Consumer Perception; Traditional Textiles; Artisan Collaboration; Cultural Heritage; Ethical Fashion; Sustainable Fashion

Impact of AI-Enabled HR Training Platforms on Employee Environmental Awareness and Sustainable Work Practices

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of Artificial Intelligence-enabled HR training platforms on employee environmental awareness and the adoption of sustainable work practices within organizations. As sustainability becomes a strategic priority, organizations increasingly leverage digital technologies to promote environmentally responsible behavior among employees. The objective of this research is to assess how AI-driven training interventions influence employees' environmental understanding, attitudes, and workplace practices. The study adopts a quantitative research design, collecting primary data through structured questionnaires administered to employees and HR professionals across organizations utilizing AI-based training platforms. The analysis employs statistical techniques including correlation, regression, and analysis of variance to evaluate relationships among variables. The findings indicate that AI-enabled training platforms significantly enhance environmental awareness and encourage the adoption of sustainable work practices. The results further demonstrate a positive relationship between AI-driven training effectiveness and pro-environmental behaviour, highlighting its role as a key component of Green HRM initiatives. The study also emphasizes the importance of personalized and interactive learning systems in fostering eco-conscious mindsets and responsible resource utilization. From a managerial perspective, the findings suggest that organizations should integrate AI technologies into HR practices to support sustainability goals. The research contributes to the literature by linking artificial intelligence, employee development, and environmental sustainability, offering insights into how digital training platforms can drive organizational and social impact.

Keywords: AI-Enabled HR Training; Environmental Awareness; Sustainable Work Practices; Green HRM; Organizational Sustainability

Factors Impacting the Consumer Choices While Purchasing the TMT Re-Bars for Home Construction

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Abstract

Commodity markets are traditionally characterized by functional parity and price-based competition, leading to the assumption that consumer decision-making is predominantly rational and economically driven. Challenging this assumption, the present study theorizes and empirically tests a multi-dimensional framework of purchase intention in the Thermo-Mechanically Treated (TMT) steel rebar market in India. Drawing upon the Theory of Consumption Values and contemporary brand trust literature, this research integrates functional, psychological, and contextual determinants of purchase intention within a unified moderated-mediation model. Using a mixed-method design (survey $n = 97$; experiments $n = 189$), the study employs regression analysis, ANOVA, and PROCESS-based mediation and moderated-mediation models. The findings reveal that while pricing exerts a significant direct effect on purchase intention, brand image operates both directly and indirectly through brand trust, particularly among urban consumers. Functional attributes such as quality and sustainability influence purchase intention only through value-based mediators, including resilience and altruistic value.

The results challenge the dominant price-centric narrative of commodity marketing and contribute to the theoretical advancement of psychological differentiation in standardized product categories. The study offers meaningful managerial implications for branding strategies in the TMT rebar industry.

Keywords: Purchase Intention; Brand Trust; Commodity Marketing; Pricing Strategy; Consumer Behaviour.

Determinants of Purchase Intention in Commodity Markets: The Role of Pricing, Brand Image, and Trust in the Indian Steel Industry

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Abstract

The steel industry plays a fundamental role in economic development and infrastructure growth, particularly in emerging economies such as India. Traditionally, steel products have been treated as commodity goods with limited differentiation, where purchasing decisions are primarily driven by price and availability. However, the rapid transformation of markets through digitalization, sustainability initiatives, and evolving consumer awareness has significantly altered the dynamics of commodity marketing. In recent years, sustainable marketing practices and digital engagement strategies have emerged as critical factors influencing consumer purchase intention even in industrial sectors.

This study investigates the determinants of purchase intention for branded steel products in the Indian retail market by integrating traditional marketing factors with sustainable marketing and digital communication perspectives. The research examines the impact of brand awareness, retail store presence, distribution network strength, perceived product quality, price perception, and sustainability orientation on consumer purchase intention. The study adopts a quantitative research approach using structured questionnaires administered to consumers involved in residential construction decisions across Tier-2 and Tier-3 cities in India. The sample consists of 150 respondents from Karnataka and Maharashtra.

Statistical analysis was conducted using correlation analysis and multivariate regression techniques. The results indicate that brand awareness, perceived product quality, price competitiveness, and sustainability perception significantly influence purchase intention. Among these variables, brand awareness and perceived product quality emerged as the strongest predictors of purchase intention. The findings highlight that sustainable marketing initiatives and digital engagement can enhance brand perception and consumer trust in commodity markets.

The study contributes to the growing literature on sustainable marketing and industrial consumer behavior by demonstrating that sustainability communication and digital marketing strategies can influence purchasing decisions even in traditionally price-driven markets. The research provides practical implications for steel manufacturers seeking to strengthen their retail presence and improve consumer engagement through sustainable and digitally enabled marketing practices.

Keywords: Sustainable marketing, purchase intention, steel industry, digital marketing, commodity markets, brand awareness.

A Study on Sustainable Tourism in South India

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Abstract

This paper reviews existing literature on sustainable tourism practices and their implementation across the tourism sector of South India. The interplay between environmental conservation, socio-cultural preservation, and economic development is examined through the three foundational pillars of sustainable tourism, analyzing how responsible tourism strategies influence destination management and community welfare. The review establishes a direct connection between sustainable tourism adoption and regional development outcomes, highlighting how eco-friendly initiatives, community-based tourism models, and responsible traveler behavior contribute to long-term ecological and socio-economic sustainability.

However, while sustainable tourism frameworks are gaining traction globally, current research remains predominantly focused on well-established destinations and urban tourism contexts. Consequently, a critical research gap exists regarding the unique challenges faced by ecologically sensitive regions in South India specifically the Western Ghats biodiversity hotspots, coastal destinations, and rural heritage sites which are rarely examined within the broader framework of environmental sustainability and community participation.

Addressing these gaps requires a comprehensive understanding of the barriers to effective implementation, including rapid urbanization, climate change impacts, inadequate waste management systems, and limited stakeholder coordination. The findings suggest that integrating policy-level interventions, digital tourism solutions, and inclusive community engagement is essential for positioning South India as a leading model for sustainable tourism development.

Keywords: Sustainable Tourism, South India, Environmental Conservation, Community-Based Tourism, Eco-Tourism, Responsible Tourism.

Sustainable Tourism Development in Goa: Examining the Role of Sustainability Dimensions and Tourism Practices

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Abstract

Sustainable tourism has emerged as a critical approach for balancing economic growth, environmental protection, and socio-cultural preservation in tourism destinations. One such destination is Goa, one of the most popular coastal tourism regions in India. Known for its beaches, heritage sites, and vibrant culture, Goa attracts millions of domestic and international tourists each year. This study aims to develop and examine a comprehensive framework for sustainable tourism in Goa by analyzing the influence of key sustainability dimensions on tourism outcomes. These factors collectively influence sustainable tourism practices, which in turn affect sustainable tourism outcomes such as environmental conservation, community well-being, tourist satisfaction, and long-term destination competitiveness. The study integrates concepts from sustainable tourism and responsible tourism management to better understand the relationships between sustainability practices and tourism outcomes.

A quantitative research methodology is adopted to test the proposed conceptual framework. Primary data are collected using a structured questionnaire designed with Likert-scale items measuring tourists' perceptions of sustainability practices and tourism outcomes. The collected data are analyzed using statistical tools to examine the relationships among the proposed constructs. Initially, reliability and descriptive analysis are conducted using SPSS to ensure the consistency and validity of the measurement items. Subsequently, the structural relationships between variables are tested using Smart PLS through the application of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling. The conceptual model proposes that environmental sustainability, socio-cultural sustainability, and economic sustainability positively influence sustainable tourism practices. These sustainability dimensions are expected to promote responsible tourism practices such as eco-conscious travel behavior, sustainable destination management, and environmentally responsible hospitality practices. These outcomes include improved environmental protection, enhanced tourist satisfaction, increased destination loyalty, and long-term competitiveness of the tourism destination. By adopting sustainable practices, tourism stakeholders can reduce the negative impacts of tourism while maximizing its economic and social benefits.

Keywords: Sustainable Tourism, Environmental Sustainability, Socio-Cultural Sustainability, Economic Sustainability, Sustainable Tourism Practices.

Digital Immersion for Sustainable Consumption: The Role of Augmented Reality in Transforming Customer Experiences

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Abstract

Augmented Reality has evolved from a mere novelty feature to a strategic tool that significantly enhances consumer evaluation, immersive experience, and decision-making in digital environments. Despite its growing adoption, limited research has examined how technology-driven immersion influences sustainable consumption behavior. Addressing this gap, the present study investigates the role of digital immersion facilitated by augmented reality in promoting sustainable online consumption. Grounded in established behavioral frameworks, the study aims to understand the relationships between augmented reality experience, digital immersion, customer engagement, and overall customer experience in shaping sustainable consumption outcomes. A quantitative research design was adopted, and data were collected from 127 online consumers. Structural equation modeling was employed to test the hypothesized relationships among the constructs. The findings indicate that augmented reality experience has a strong positive influence on digital immersion. Furthermore, digital immersion indirectly impacts sustainable online consumption through enhanced customer engagement and enriched customer experience. These results highlight the mediating role of engagement and experience in translating immersive technology into sustainable behavioral outcomes. The study contributes to academic literature by integrating immersive technology with sustainability perspectives in consumer behavior research. From a managerial standpoint, the findings provide actionable insights for marketers and digital platform designers to develop immersive and sustainability-oriented strategies that encourage responsible consumption patterns in online environments.

Keywords: Augmented Reality; Customer Experience; Digital Immersion; Online Customer Engagement; Sustainable Consumption

Community-Led Digital Platforms and Inclusive Growth in Rural Eco-Tourism: The Mediating Role of Community Empowerment

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Abstract

Rural eco-tourism is increasingly positioned as a pathway for sustainable local development; however, its benefits often remain unevenly distributed as external intermediaries capture a disproportionate share of value while local communities struggle to convert digital connectivity into locally retained gains. Although digital transformation can enhance visibility, coordination, and market access in rural tourism, its developmental outcomes depend more on governance structures, local capabilities, and community empowerment than on technology adoption alone. Addressing this gap, the present study examines whether community-led digital platforms can serve as a mechanism through which digital transformation contributes to inclusive growth in rural eco-tourism. Integrating the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology 2 with a community empowerment perspective, the study argues that technology adoption must strengthen local agency, participation, and value capture to generate inclusive outcomes. A quantitative research design was employed using cross-sectional survey data collected from 60 rural eco-tourism stakeholders. Regression-based path analysis with mediation and moderation testing was applied to examine the hypothesized relationships. The findings indicate that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions significantly influence the adoption of community-led digital platforms. Platform adoption strongly predicts community empowerment, while both platform adoption and empowerment positively affect inclusive growth. The mediation analysis reveals partial mediation, highlighting empowerment as a key mechanism linking digital transformation to inclusive development. The moderating effect of government support was positive but not statistically significant. The study contributes to sustainable tourism literature by reframing digital transformation as a community-governed value redistribution mechanism and offers implications for policymakers and practitioners aiming to strengthen rural participation and reduce economic leakage.

Keywords: Rural eco-tourism; Inclusive growth; Community-led digital platforms; Community empowerment; Digital transformation; UTAUT2; Sustainable tourism; Rural development

Influence in the Digital Age: A Systematic and Bibliometric Review of Micro-Influencer Marketing and Generation Z's Sustainable Fashion Consumption

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Abstract

The growing environmental impact of the fashion industry has intensified the need to understand sustainable consumption behavior, particularly among Generation Z. Despite high levels of awareness, a persistent intention–behavior gap continues to challenge the adoption of sustainable fashion practices. At the same time, the rapid expansion of social media has elevated micro-influencers as credible and relatable agents who significantly shape consumer perceptions and decision-making processes. Addressing this intersection, the present study adopts a dual-method approach by integrating bibliometric analysis with a systematic literature review to examine the role of micro-influencer marketing in promoting sustainable fashion consumption. Bibliometric data were sourced from the Scopus database using a structured search strategy, yielding 174 peer-reviewed articles published between 2019 and 2025. Analytical techniques, including keyword co-occurrence and density visualization, were conducted to map the intellectual structure of the domain. Complementing this, a PRISMA-based systematic literature review of 60 studies was undertaken to synthesize theoretical frameworks, dominant themes, and existing research gaps. The findings identify three primary research clusters: influencer-driven sustainability communication, intention-based consumer behavior models, and emerging technological mediation in digital environments. While the literature is predominantly grounded in established behavioral theories, limited integration across frameworks is evident. The study proposes an integrated perspective linking media engagement, influencer credibility, and behavioral intention formation. The research contributes to both academic and managerial domains by offering a structured understanding of digital influence mechanisms and providing strategic insights for sustainable fashion marketing initiatives.

Keywords: Micro-influencer marketing; Sustainable fashion; Generation Z; Social media; Consumer behavior; Bibliometric analysis; Systematic literature review

Forecasting Crypto Funding Rates for Risk Monitoring

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Abstract

Cryptocurrency perpetual futures have emerged as one of the most actively traded instruments in digital asset markets, primarily due to their ability to support leveraged positions without a fixed expiry date. A key feature of these instruments is the funding rate mechanism, which facilitates periodic payments between long and short traders to maintain price alignment with the underlying spot market. Beyond its pricing function, the funding rate serves as a critical indicator of market imbalance, leverage concentration, and short-term trading sentiment. Despite its importance, limited research has focused on forecasting short-horizon funding rates and integrating such forecasts into practical risk-monitoring systems. Addressing this gap, the present study aims to develop a framework for forecasting funding rates in major cryptocurrency perpetual contracts using market-driven inputs. The study adopts a quantitative approach, leveraging historical market data and predictive modeling techniques to estimate short-term funding rate movements. Additionally, the research proposes an analyst-oriented dashboard that translates forecast outputs into actionable insights for monitoring funding risk and exposure. The expected findings highlight the feasibility of predicting funding rate trends and demonstrate how these forecasts can enhance risk awareness, support decision-making, and improve the management of leveraged trading strategies. This study contributes to the growing literature on cryptocurrency derivatives by linking predictive analytics with applied risk management and offers practical implications for traders, analysts, and financial institutions operating in digital asset markets.

Keywords: Cryptocurrency Perpetual Futures, Funding Rate Forecasting, Risk Monitoring, Analyst Dashboard, Short-Horizon Forecasting, Crypto Derivatives, Funding Risk

Impact of Real-Time Trading Apps on Students' Investment Habits

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of real-time trading applications on the investment habits of students in India, with specific reference to widely used platforms such as Zerodha and Groww. Grounded in an extended Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology framework and supported by Social Learning Theory, Nudge Theory, Choice Architecture, and Human Capital and Financial Literacy perspectives, the research investigates the influence of performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, use behaviour, and voluntariness of use on students' investment habits. A quantitative research design was adopted, and primary data were collected from 131 valid respondents comprising undergraduate, postgraduate, and professional course students through a structured questionnaire administered during February and March 2026. Reliability analysis yielded a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.926, and the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin measure of sampling adequacy was 0.874, indicating strong instrument validity. One-sample t-tests revealed that all constructs were significantly above the neutral midpoint. Hypothesis testing using simple linear regression confirmed that all six proposed relationships were statistically significant at $p = 0.001$. Among the predictors, voluntariness of use emerged as the strongest determinant of use behaviour, followed by use behaviour itself and facilitating conditions. The findings also indicate that Groww is the most preferred platform due to its ease of use. The study highlights that students are increasingly adopting disciplined, platform-driven investment practices influenced by intrinsic motivation and ease of access. The research contributes to the literature on financial technology adoption and offers practical implications for platform developers, financial educators, and regulatory bodies in enhancing responsible investment behavior.

Keywords: Real-Time Trading Applications; Investment Habits; Financial Technology; Student Investors; Behaviour; Regulation

Foreign Direct Investment, Trade Openness and Environmental Sustainability in India: An ARDL Analysis with Structural Breaks

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Abstract

The present study empirically investigates the causal relationship among foreign direct investment inflows, economic growth, trade openness, and carbon dioxide emissions in India over the period 1980 to 2023 using the autoregressive distributed lag modeling framework. Addressing limitations in prior research, the study incorporates structural breaks identified through multiple breakpoint tests into the analysis to improve robustness and capture regime shifts in the time-series data. The cointegration results confirm the existence of a significant long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables. Further, the error correction model with structural breaks reveals a bidirectional causal relationship between foreign direct investment inflows and trade openness, supporting the existence of a complementary long-term association. However, no significant long-run causation is observed between foreign direct investment and economic growth. In the short run, a bidirectional relationship between foreign direct investment and economic growth is identified, although the magnitude of impact remains modest. The results also indicate that economic growth and trade openness contribute to increased carbon dioxide emissions, whereas foreign direct investment inflows do not exhibit a statistically significant relationship with emissions in either the short or long run. Consequently, the findings do not support the pollution haven hypothesis in the Indian context. The study contributes to the environmental economics literature by integrating structural break analysis within the autoregressive distributed lag framework and provides policy implications emphasizing the need to promote environmentally sustainable and green-oriented foreign direct investment rather than purely employment-driven inflows.

Keywords: Foreign Direct Investment; Economic Growth; Trade Openness; CO₂ Emissions; ARDL Approach; India

Impact of Greenwashing on Consumer Green Trust in the Beauty Industry: A Focus on Female Consumers

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Abstract

The rapid growth of the beauty industry, coupled with increasing consumer awareness of sustainability, has intensified concerns regarding greenwashing practices. This study investigates the impact of greenwashing on consumer green trust, with a specific focus on female consumers in the Indian beauty market. It further examines the role of social influence and product accessibility factors in shaping trust toward environmentally positioned products. The study adopts a quantitative research design using a structured questionnaire distributed among female consumers, yielding 204 valid responses. A conceptual framework incorporating greenwashing awareness, perceived credibility of environmental claims, product accessibility factors, and social influence was developed and tested. Statistical techniques including factor analysis, correlation analysis, and reliability testing were employed to validate the constructs and examine relationships among variables.

The findings reveal that product accessibility factors and social influence have a significant positive impact on consumer green trust, indicating that availability, affordability, peer influence, and social media engagement play a crucial role in shaping trust perceptions. In contrast, greenwashing awareness and perceived credibility of environmental claims demonstrate weaker direct effects on consumer trust. This suggests the presence of an attitude-behaviour gap, where awareness of misleading claims does not necessarily translate into trust-related decision-making. The study contributes to green marketing literature by highlighting the relative importance of practical and social drivers over cognitive awareness in building consumer trust. Managerially, the findings emphasize the need for brands to enhance product accessibility and leverage credible social influence while maintaining transparency in sustainability communication. The study also provides implications for policymakers to strengthen regulatory frameworks to curb deceptive environmental claims.

Keywords: Greenwashing; Consumer Green Trust; Beauty Industry; Social Influence; Product Accessibility; Female Consumers

Sustainability Perceptions in Luxury Hospitality: A Comparative Analysis of Generation Z and Baby Boomers Across Hotels and Luxury Homestays

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Abstract

Sustainability has emerged as a critical strategic factor in the luxury hospitality sector, influencing customer perceptions, value evaluations, and behavioural intentions. This study examines how sustainability is perceived across generational cohorts specifically Generation Z and Baby Boomers within luxury hotels and luxury homestays. Grounded in the Value-Belief-Norm (VBN) theory and the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), the study investigates the influence of environmental concern, perceived green value, and perceived luxury value on intention to stay.

A quantitative comparative research design was adopted using a structured dataset of 400 observations, balanced across generational cohorts and accommodation formats. Analytical techniques including descriptive analysis, t-tests, correlation, and structural relationship assessment were employed to evaluate differences and relationships among key constructs. The findings reveal a significant generational divide: Generation Z demonstrates higher environmental concern and perceived green value, whereas Baby Boomers place greater emphasis on perceived luxury value and exhibit a stronger overall intention to stay.

Further, accommodation-type comparisons indicate that luxury hotels maintain stronger associations with premium service and exclusivity, while luxury homestays show a modest advantage in perceived green value. Structural relationships confirm that environmental concern strongly predicts perceived green value, and that the influence of green and luxury value on behavioural intention varies significantly across generations.

The study contributes to sustainable hospitality literature by integrating generational segmentation with value-based frameworks and offering a dual-value perspective on luxury consumption. Managerially, the findings suggest that hospitality providers should adopt segment-specific sustainability strategies, aligning environmental initiatives with differentiated customer expectations to enhance engagement, trust, and competitive positioning.

Keywords: Sustainable Hospitality; Luxury Hotels; Luxury Homestays; Generation Z; Baby Boomers; Perceived Green Value

Technology-Driven Talent Management and Strategic Marketing Performance: Mediating Role of Organizational Sustainability in the IT Industry

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Abstract

The rapid adoption of digital technologies in human resource management has transformed talent acquisition, development, and retention practices in the IT industry. However, the interrelationship between technology-driven talent management, organizational sustainability, and strategic marketing performance remains underexplored. Grounded in the Resource-Based View (RBV) and Dynamic Capabilities Theory, this study aims to examine the mediating role of organizational sustainability in the relationship between technology-driven talent management and strategic marketing performance.

A quantitative research design was adopted using survey data collected from 234 IT professionals across domains such as software development, SaaS, IT consulting, telecommunications, and IT-enabled services in Bengaluru. The data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) to test the hypothesized relationships. The results indicate that technology-driven talent management has a significant positive effect on both organizational sustainability and strategic marketing performance. Furthermore, organizational sustainability significantly influences marketing performance and partially mediates the relationship between talent management and marketing outcomes.

The findings suggest that technology-driven talent management functions as a dynamic capability that enhances marketing performance through both direct and indirect pathways. The study contributes to the literature by integrating human resource management, sustainability, and marketing performance within a unified framework, particularly in the IT sector context. From a managerial perspective, the results emphasize the importance of aligning digital talent strategies with sustainability initiatives to achieve competitive marketing advantages. The study concludes that organizations leveraging technology-driven talent management alongside sustainability practices are better positioned to enhance long-term performance and strategic competitiveness.

Keywords: Technology-Driven Talent Management; Organizational Sustainability; Strategic Marketing Performance; IT Industry; PLS-SEM; Dynamic Capabilities

Marketing in the Age of Artificial Intelligence and Emerging Technologies: A Qualitative Systematic Review

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Abstract

The contemporary marketing landscape is undergoing rapid transformation driven by Artificial Intelligence (AI) and emerging technologies such as generative AI, agentic AI, predictive analytics, and hyper-personalization. This study aims to systematically synthesize the impact of AI on marketing practices and evolving consumer engagement strategies within technology-driven marketplaces. Adopting a qualitative systematic literature review approach, the study examines peer-reviewed research published over the past decade across Scopus, Web of Science, and ABDC-indexed journals. An initial pool of 483 articles was refined to 51 relevant studies through rigorous screening and thematic classification using the TCCM (Theory–Context–Characteristics–Methodology) framework.

The findings identify key themes including data-driven decision-making, digital transformation, customer-centric strategies, and the growing integration of emerging technologies in marketing ecosystems. The analysis reveals that AI is shifting marketing from reactive, intuition-based approaches to proactive, predictive, and highly personalized strategies. Technologies such as conversational AI, recommender systems, and big data analytics significantly enhance customer engagement, campaign effectiveness, and value creation. At the same time, the study highlights critical challenges related to data privacy, ethical concerns, governance, and skill gaps.

The research contributes to the literature by offering an integrative framework that consolidates fragmented insights and clarifies the interrelationship between AI-driven technologies and marketing strategy. From a managerial perspective, the study provides actionable insights for organizations to realign marketing strategies in response to dynamic market conditions and stakeholder expectations. It concludes by outlining future research directions emphasizing the need for empirical validation and sustainable AI adoption practices.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Consumer Engagement; Technology-Enabled Marketing; Agentic AI; Predictive Analytics; Hyper-Personalization

Inclusive Visual Merchandising: Integrating Environmental Psychology and Marketing for Multicultural Retail Spaces

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Abstract

Retail environments are increasingly expected to do more than attract consumers; they must also affirm diverse social and cultural identities. While existing literature on servicescapes and retail atmospherics highlights the impact of physical environments on consumer perceptions and behavior, inclusivity remains underexplored as a core design principle. This conceptual paper addresses this gap by integrating environmental psychology with inclusive marketing to develop a framework for identity-affirming retail environments.

Drawing upon the Servicescape Model and Identity-Based Motivation Theory, the study examines how visual and spatial elements such as lighting, multilingual signage, and inclusive representation through mannequins shape consumer perceptions of belonging, emotional engagement, and brand loyalty. The research adopts a conceptual methodology based on systematic synthesis of secondary literature from established academic databases, enabling interdisciplinary integration across marketing, psychology, and cultural studies.

The proposed framework positions inclusivity as a mediating mechanism between retail design and consumer behavioral outcomes. It argues that inclusive visual merchandising not only enhances customer experience but also serves as a strategic tool for fostering trust and long-term loyalty in multicultural markets.

The study contributes theoretically by extending servicescape literature to incorporate inclusivity as an intrinsic design dimension, and managerially by offering actionable insights for retailers to create culturally responsive and identity-affirming environments. While the framework is not empirically tested, it provides a strong foundation for future research involving experimental and cross-cultural validation.

Keywords: inclusive marketing; visual merchandising; servicescape; identity-based motivation; multicultural retail

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